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TRACKING ILLNESS RELATED CHRONIC ABSENCE:
A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

School attendance is a predictor of academic achievement, which in turn is a determinant of future health and employment opportunities. Chronic absenteeism, defined as missing 10% or more school days regardless of reason (excused or unexcused), affects 13% of students nationwide. District attendance processes, policies, and data were analyzed in a demographically diverse Southern California high school. A comparison of attendance processes between the school site and four other districts was conducted to identify the differences in practices. A review of the attendance history of 117 ninth and tenth graders, who missed at least 10% of days in school, showed that 66% of the absences were due to illness. Seventy-seven students met the criteria for moderate to severe illness chronic absence, and 14% of these students failed one or more classes in the first semester. A school nurse referral process with an accompanying algorithm, a chronic absence district policy, a chronic illness verification form, and pilot project proposal were developed to facilitate an improved process of identifying students at risk of illness-related chronic absences prior to the negative consequence to academic performance. Emerging evidence highlights the impact school nurses have in the reduction of absenteeism rates in students with chronic conditions. School nurses have an integral role in mitigating illness related chronic absences through case coordination efforts. Thus, developing an attendance tracking system which monitors illness related chronic absences and includes the school nurse in the intervention plan may prevent the need for more intensive strategies and promote academic achievement.

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BACKGROUND

Nationwide 13% of all students miss fifteen or more school days during the school year, and more than 18% are chronically absent (U.S. Department of Education, Office of Civil Rights, 2016). The California Attorney General (2016) reported that 7% of elementary students missed 10% of the 2015-2016 school year, leaving these students at risk for school failure and dropout. Chronic absenteeism, defined as missing 10% or more school days regardless of reason (excused or unexcused), leads to adverse long-term effects including employment problems, lower health literacy, higher rates of illness, and earlier deaths (Allensworth, Lewallen, Stevenson, & Katz, 2011; California Attorney General, 2016; U.S. Department of Justice, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development, & U.S. Department of Education, 2015).

Bruner, Discher, and Chang (2011) analyzed the relationship between the average daily attendance (ADA) and chronic absence rates of elementary schools in three urban districts and found that ADA, the most common method of calculating attendance, may fail in the detection of high levels of chronic absences. The ADA tracking method is ineffective because it does not identify patterns of absenteeism, and it cannot explain or predict the extent of chronic absenteeism rates (Bruner et al., 2011). Therefore, Bruner et al. (2011) recommended that schools with a 93-97% ADA rate analyze absenteeism patterns and develop appropriate interventions. The ADA rate for a district with 54,000 students in a California suburb is 96% (Ed-Data, 2017). However, this data may not be the best indicator of good school attendance because it does not measure chronic absenteeism rates (Bruner et al., 2011).

Problem Statement

Illness is a common excuse provided by parents when reporting an absence, yet many attendance tracking systems do not specifically identify illness absences (Jacobsen, Meeder, & Voskil, 2016; Kerr et al., 2002). Absences are coded simply as excused, an absence that has been verified as legitimate, or unexcused (truancy). The lack of an illness code prevents tracking of these absences and limits the ability of school nurses to initiate early assessment and interventions that may ensure absences do not impede learning. Emerging evidence highlights the impact school nurses have in the reduction of absenteeism rates in students with chronic conditions, such as asthma, diabetes, and psychosocial problems (Rodriguez et al., 2014). The lack of a formal procedure for tracking illness absences and an associated school nurse referral process for early intervention leaves students at risk for the short- and long-term effects of chronic absenteeism.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to promote student health and maximize potential educational outcomes through an improved attendance tracking system that identifies students at risk of illness-related chronic absences and activates a school nurse referral when the 10% illness chronic absence threshold is reached. The goals were as follows:

1. Establish an attendance tracking system that allows coding of illness as a reason for an absence (i.e., medical/dental appointment, illness or hospitalization).
2. Develop a protocol that would trigger a referral for nursing evaluation and intervention.

Supporting Framework

School nursing originated in 1902 with the appointment of Lina Rogers who provided health services to 8,671 students in four separate schools in New York City (American Academy of Pediatrics [AAP] Council on School Health, 2016). At the turn of the century, students were often medically exempted from school due to untreated contagious diseases, which resulted in high absenteeism rates (Schumacher, 2002). The comparison of absenteeism records from October 1902 to September 1903, revealed a 99% reduction in student absences (from 10,567 to 1,101) within one year of Rogers' appointment, highlighting the impact of the school nurse (AAP Council on School Health, 2016; Schumacher, 2002). The successful nursing intervention led to the decision by the New York City Board of Health to hire twelve additional nurses (Schumacher, 2002). Rogers paved the way by demonstrating that school nurses can be instrumental in promoting academic success through improved school attendance.

In recent years, the increased prevalence and complexity of students' health needs, and changes in healthcare evoked the need for a School Nurse framework that provides practice focus and structure in the delivery of evidence-based nursing services (National Association of School Nurses [NASN], 2016). The Framework for 21st Century School Nursing was developed to establish five integral principles that create a strong foundation for quality nursing care delivered in the school setting. The five principles include Standards of Practice, Care Coordination, Leadership, Quality Improvement (QI), and Community/Public Health. This framework provided the overarching structure that guided this quality improvement project. Two principles, Care Coordination and QI are highlighted in this change process to effectively identify

students at risk for illness related chronic absenteeism and generate a referral for nursing evaluation and intervention. Implementation of this change project applied these principles in conjunction with the Focus, Analyze, Develop, Execute, and Evaluate (FADE) model, which provided the structural process for the project (Duke University School of Medicine, 2016).

Quality Improvement (QI) is defined as a formal approach to improve quality of care through performance analysis and process development (Duke University School of Medicine, 2016). The FADE model, a cyclical process that involves a trial and learning approach, is one of the most common methods utilized by the healthcare industry to improve quality of care (Wickman, Drake, Heilmann, Rojas, & Jarvis, 2013).

FADE is the most suitable methodology for this project because it will provide a framework that will facilitate quality improvement through an iterative process. In the Focus stage, the process needing improvement will be defined and verified to substantiate that a problem exists. Current district attendance tracking and monitoring practices will be reviewed. These practices will be compared with those of other districts. A national conference will be attended to gain knowledge about how two California districts have integrated school nurses in their plan to mitigate chronic absence.

Data review is a cornerstone of QI. During the Analyze stage, baseline data is obtained, a root cause analysis is conducted, and probable solutions are identified (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services Health Resources and Services Administration, 2011). An attendance report will be generated to identify ninth and tenth-grade students with moderate to severe chronic absence (missed 10% or more of the school year).

In the Develop phase, a solution to the problem and plan for implementation are formulated (Barton, Danek, Johns, & Coons, 1998). Findings from the Analyze phase will guide the development of proposals to improve attendance-tracking practices. Key stakeholders will be identified and included in development of an implementation plan.

The pilot project proposal will be presented to key district administrators during the Execute phase. The proposal will include findings drawn from the Analyze phase and a proposal for early identification and intervention in students with moderate chronic absence. During the final phase, Evaluate, it is important to implement a process control system that will monitor and measure success. An evaluation plan to measure the effectiveness of the pilot project will be developed.

Figure 1. Modified FADE and 21st Century School Nursing Practice Framework to facilitate change through an iterative process with the aim of reducing chronic absenteeism.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A search of the literature focused on attendance tracking systems, effects of chronic absenteeism on health and education outcomes, and school nurse involvement in addressing absenteeism was performed. The databases accessed to conduct the search of literature included PubMed, CINAHL, ERIC, and EBSCO. Key search terms included absenteeism, attendance tracking, attendance tracking systems, chronic absenteeism, care coordination, case management, chronic health conditions children/pediatrics, FADE, quality improvement, quality improvement models, school nurse*, school nurse framework, and truancy used in different combinations. The literature search was limited to English language only and peer-reviewed journals published between 2000-2017.

Chronic Absenteeism

School attendance is a predictor of academic achievement, which in turn is a determinant of future health and employment opportunities (Allensworth et al., 2011; California Attorney General, 2016; Crump et al., 2013). Absenteeism is a warning sign for high-risk behaviors, such as tobacco use, drug abuse, high-risk sexual behaviors, and violence (Eaton, Brener, & Kann, 2008; Vaughn, Maynard, Salas-Wright, Perron, & Abdon, 2013).

Since 2013, the California Attorney General's Office has compiled an annual report that examines the prevalence and impact of chronic absenteeism (Attendance Works, 2014). For the first time, the California Department of Education will require all local education agencies (LEAs) to submit student absence data at the end of the 2016-2017 school year (State of California, Department of Justice, 2017). Furthermore,

California's new accountability system will require LEAs to submit Local Control Accountability Plans (LCAP) outlining efforts to mitigate chronic absenteeism (Attendance Works, 2014; State of California, Department of Justice, 2017). Since illness is the most common reason for absences, closely monitoring students who have reached the 10% absence threshold due to "illness" is important.

Short, Marriott, Ostroff, and Waller (2011) evaluated a school monitoring system that tracked cases of illness absences, specifically influenza-like symptoms, for surveillance of pandemic influenza A (pH1N1) and found that absence records were not a reliable tool for tracking illness absences. The high response rate to their survey, which determined the interest level of schools in continuing the process, suggested that school sites value tracking illness absences because absences affect educational activities (Short et al., 2011). Genoa (2015) examined attendance data as an indicator of high school transition success and reported that the identification of students at risk for poor academic outcomes is dependent on access to reliable and readily available data.

The prevalence of asthma is documented by school districts, yet asthma-related absences are not captured by the current attendance tracking system. Lack of data inhibits the ability to identify school-level interventions that would decrease absenteeism related to asthma (Raun et al., 2017). Therefore, establishing a system that explicitly codes illness absences would improve efforts to mitigate them and appropriately target resources, such as school nurse and teacher interventions. The lack of a system that explicitly codes illness absences impedes the implementation of early intervention strategies.

Chronic Health Conditions

Chronic health conditions, defined as conditions with duration of three months or more, have increased in prevalence amongst U.S. children in the last fifty years and affects 15-20% of students in the U.S. (Crump et al., 2013; Rivkina et al., 2014). The existence of a chronic health condition poses increased risks for poor educational attainment and unsuccessful high school completion (Bonilla et al., 2005; Champaloux & Young, 2015; Crump et al., 2013; Krenitsky-Korn, 2011). Raun et. al (2017) reported that fifty percent of children with chronic illness miss a significant amount of school days due to physical and/or social effects associated with their condition. Absences could be attributed to symptom flare-ups, medical appointments, side effects of the treatment regimen, or perceptions of feeling "different" (Raun et al., 2017). The high rates of absenteeism negatively affect learning due to missed classroom instruction (Krenitsky-Korn, 2011). Crump et al. (2013) concluded that low school achievement is strongly associated with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and seizure disorders, but not as strongly with cardiovascular disorders, diabetes or asthma. Children with ADHD, seizures, cardiovascular disorders, diabetes, or asthma have a 1.3 times higher risk of absenteeism (Crump et al., 2013).

Asthma, the most common childhood chronic health condition affects 8.4% U.S. children under the age of 18 (Bonilla et al., 2005; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2017; Krenitsky-Korn, 2011; Moonie, Sterling, Figgs & Castro, 2006; Rivkina et al., 2014). Prevalence of asthma is higher amongst African Americans and in families with low socioeconomic status, which intensifies the risks for academic failure in these already high-risk population groups (Moonie, Sterling, Figgs, & Castro, 2006).

Students with asthma have higher rates of absenteeism and are two times more likely to miss school due to illness (Champaloux & Young, 2015; CDC, 2015; Meng, Babey, & Wolstein, 2012; Rodriguez et al., 2013). The high absenteeism rates may be indicative of greater asthma severity and/or inadequate asthma control (Bonilla et al., 2005). Asthma is also a leading cause of pediatric hospitalizations and accounts for 10.5 million lost school days nationwide (Raun et al., 2017).

Emerson et al. (2016) reported that the parents of children with chronic illness might extend absences due to an increased perception of vulnerability in their child. School nurses have the opportunity intervene in these circumstances by educating families about the importance of regular school attendance, and by coordinating care specific to the student's health needs.

Care Coordination by School Nurses

Reported illness chronic absences are questioned only when the student's academic status has been noticeably impacted, and the school nurse is rarely consulted in these circumstances. The lack of a formalized process to elicit a school nurse referral to address illness absences results in missed early intervention opportunities (Weismuller, Grasska, Alexander, White, & Kramer, 2007). School Nurses can be instrumental in intervention efforts to curtail chronic absenteeism through the application of care coordination processes, a key principle of the School Nurse Framework (NASN, 2016). Care coordination includes assessment of the student's health status, collaborative communication with the student's caretaker(s) and healthcare provider, and development and implementation of the health plan (McClanahan & Weismuller, 2015). Scientific knowledge, case management experience, and a holistic approach to care enable school

nurses to effectively employ care coordination efforts in managing chronic health conditions.

Care coordination by a school nurse can improve disease management in students with poorly controlled asthma, and thus, reduce missed school days and emergency room visits (Rodriguez, et. al, 2013). Optimal management of asthma includes identifying gaps and improving asthma management (Szeffler, 2010). According to Kruzick et al. (2009), children still have poor asthma control despite having access to care. Medication adherence is particularly challenging for adolescents, placing them at risk for asthma morbidity (Szeffler, 2010). Therefore, the identification and monitoring of high-risk students are significant in preventing asthma morbidity and improving outcomes. Since children spend at least six hours in school, it is an ideal setting for the identification of students with asthma risks, those with poor asthma control, and for teaching self-management skills (Szeffler, 2010). Krenistsky-Korn (2011) concluded that school nurse interventions decreased the early parent pick up from school and decreased the loss of instruction due to the physical, social, emotional and academic support.

METHODS

The purpose of this quality improvement project was to promote student health and maximize potential educational outcomes through an improved attendance tracking system that identifies students at risk of chronic absence due to illness and initiates a school nurse referral process. Through the application of the FADE framework, district attendance processes, policies, and attendance data were analyzed in a demographically diverse Southern California high school.

No ethical concerns were identified as a review of existing records poses minimal risks to students. Parental consent is not required since attendance tracking is a state mandate, and care coordination is a school nurse standard of practice.

Focus: Illness Related Chronic Absence Tracking Systems

Chronic absence due to illness is often unnoticed until academic performance is negatively impacted. The school nurse does not have the opportunity to provide nursing interventions because students with illness chronic absence are not referred for evaluation. The district's attendance practices were reviewed to gain an understanding of the attendance tracking system, how absences are classified, and the documentation practices of attendance clerks. The attendance policy and coding system were reviewed. Attendance clerks were asked about the absence verification and documentation practices. Since the school nurse has four school sites, the health clerk is more familiar with students who frequently visit the health office and are chronically absent. The school nurse requested that the health clerk compile and relay information about frequent health office visits and chronic absence.

School nurses from four districts were consulted regarding their district chronic absence practices to determine whether their attendance monitoring system capture illness absences, and whether students are referred to the school nurse if a student has chronic absence due to illness. Current information about how other districts in California have integrated school nurses in their efforts to reduce chronic absenteeism was sought at a national school health conference focused on addressing chronic absenteeism.

Analyze: Determine the Problem

The district's attendance tracking system and practices were analyzed to identify areas with potential for improvement. Absence coding and documentation were reviewed to determine gaps in the identification of illness related chronic absences and timely intervention. A comparison of attendance tracking processes between the selected high school and four other districts was conducted to identify differences in practices. The most significant difference is that the district's current attendance coding system does not have a specific illness code, resulting in missed opportunities for early identification and intervention in at risk students. The other difference is that since illness-related chronic absence is not monitored, a school nurse referral process is lacking.

A report categorizing data by grade level and attendance category (at risk, moderate and severe absence) was generated on March 2, 2018. Definitions were operationalized to determine which cases met criteria for illness chronic and clustered absences. Records of students in the ninth or tenth grade with moderate to severe chronic absence were analyzed for gender, number of days absent, number of days absent due to illness, if absences affected academic progress, and if a School Attendance Review Team

(SART) or Student Attendance Review Board (SARB) referral was initiated. The student's health history, medical diagnosis, prescribed medications, and health office visits were also reviewed and an assessment of whether or not students with illness chronic absences were referred to the school nurse was conducted.

Develop Solutions to the Problem

It was important to include key stakeholders, such as attendance clerks, the health clerk, the principal, Information Technology (IT) specialist, and district level administrators, in the planning stage. The first phase in Develop focused on the development of an attendance tracking process that identifies illness absences. The second part of the Develop phase focused on the school nurse referral process. A proposal to improve attendance-monitoring practices at a large suburban high school was developed for pilot implementation in the next school year.

Findings from the Analyze phase resulted in the development of proposed solutions to address gaps in identifying illness absences. These gaps may potentially hinder interventions aimed at mitigating poor academic outcomes due to chronic absence. Proposed solutions focused on improving attendance tracking practices, verification of illness absences, and a school nurse referral process.

Execute and Evaluate

Based on information gathered through the previous FADE steps, a pilot project proposal, which included revised attendance codes, a chronic illness verification form, and a chronic absence policy with an algorithm, was developed and presented to the SARB coordinator, an Executive Director, the site principal, and the assistant principal who oversees attendance. The proposed pilot implementation date is August 2018 at the

selected high school for this project. An evaluation plan was developed to be employed following the pilot project implementation.

RESULTS

The FADE (Focus, Analyze, Develop, Execute) framework provided the structural process to report results of the project and facilitated a comparison of the expected goals outlined in the Methods section. A school nurse referral process with an accompanying algorithm, chronic absence district policy, two presentations, chronic illness verification form, a school nurse referral form, and a pilot project proposal were developed to facilitate an improved process of identifying students at risk of illness chronic absences prior to the negative consequence to academic performance.

Focus

To substantiate that a problem exists, the process needing improvement is defined and verified in the Focus stage of the FADE model. In an effort to mitigate chronic absenteeism, the district implemented an attendance-tracking tool in 2013. The attendance tool, known as District Attendance Tracking Tool (DATT), has the capability of generating real-time attendance data and categorizing it by grade level, gender, race/ethnicity, and level of attendance. The attendance levels include satisfactory attendance (missing less than 5% of total school days), at risk attendance (missing 5-9.99%), moderate chronic absence (missing 10-19.99%), and severely chronic absence (missing 20% or more). The tool allows school sites and the district to have a comprehensive overview of attendance data that is more descriptive than a simple average daily attendance (ADA) rate. For example, information can be gathered to determine the rate of severely chronic absent students, differentiate absence rates between grade levels, and provide the identity of absent students by each category and grade.

District Attendance Practice

Since the implementation of DATT, attendance reports have provided *valuable* information to school sites and the district. Although the new system allowed timely identification of chronically absent students, absence code definitions do not identify the specific reason for the excused or unexcused absence. Illness is one of the most common reasons for excused absences, yet there is no clear illness code. The common interpretation among attendance clerks and administrators is that illness absences are coded as "1". However, Code 1 includes illness absences, as well as absence for attendance at the funeral service of an immediate family member, for jury duty, or for a teen student who stays home to care for a sick his/her sick child. The lack of an illness code does not allow a simple method to track the reason for the chronic absences, which prevents the initiation of a school nurse referral for those students with moderate to severe illness chronic absences. Identifying the specific reason for the absence would ensure better decision-making about the proper education placement, such as online classes, or homebound instruction. Interventions to address trancies would differ from absences related to illness.

Stakeholders [the SARB coordinator, the Student Services Administrative Director, the Student Services Assistant Superintendent, site administrators, attendance clerks, health clerk, the Child and Welfare Attendance (CWA) clerk, and an IT program systems specialist] were presented with chronic absence data and the plan to implement the quality improvement pilot project. A proposal for a specific illness code was presented in order to facilitate Tier 2 interventions, such as a school nurse referral and

involvement. The school nurse interventions could potentially reduce the number of SART and SARB referrals.

Table 1

Current Attendance Codes

Excused Absence Code 1	Excused Absence Code 2
Illness or injury	Religious holiday, ceremony, or retreat
Medical, dental, optometric, psychological, or chiropractic appointment	Employment conference
Funeral service of immediate family member (Mother, father, sibling, grandparent, spouse, in-law, or any other relative living in the home.) California- 1 day Out of State- 3days	Funeral service other than excused
Jury Duty	Court appearance/probation/legal appointment/investigative hearing
Teen parent to care for sick child	Personal reason requested by parent or guardian-approved by administrator or administrative designee

Truancies are addressed in a more punitive manner. Examples of interventions to address truancy include attending Saturday school, suspension or restriction of driving privilege, or a referral to juvenile court. Legal requirements mandate that habitually truant students be referred to SARB, a truancy mediation program operated by the county's district attorney or the probation officer. SARB is a community-based effort whose focus is to provide intensive strategies to prevent the student and family from entering the court system. The district SARB team consists of the SARB chair, CWA clerk, school nurse, school counselor, school psychologist, local law enforcement, a probation officer, a representative from Child Protective Services (CPS), and a District Attorney. At SARB hearings attended by the school nurse, parents often cite illness as a

reason for chronic absence, yet the school site nurse is often unaware of the student. Monitoring these absences and interventions by the school nurse could potentially reduce the number of SARB referrals and offer interventions at an earlier point in the process.

The homebound instruction program is a short-term temporary accommodation to regular school attendance when a student has a verified medical condition that prevents school attendance. When students with illness-related chronic absence are at risk of academic failure, some parents apply for homebound instruction services in an attempt to remediate failing grades. Identifying students with illness-related chronic absences due to a verified medical condition and involving the school nurse would help ensure that homebound instruction is the most appropriate education placement. The school nurse can collaborate with the medical provider to determine what school accommodations may promote better attendance and academic performance. This process could potentially reduce the number of homebound instruction referrals because interventions would be in place to help ensure that the student does not fall behind academically.

School site and district administrators, a CWA clerk, the health clerk, and attendance clerks showed support for creating an illness code for improved attendance tracking. The Administrative Director and Assistant Superintendent provided support by allowing other departments to meet with the school nurse and to have access to attendance data. The SARB coordinator supported the addition of an illness code to better identify the reason for absences in order to establish the most effective strategy to mitigate chronic absenteeism. The CWA clerk reported that the current SARB referral process does not identify the specific reason for chronic absenteeism. Since the attendance report only indicates the number of absences, date, and if the absence is

excused or unexcused, the CWA clerk stated that a specific illness code would allow for better preparation for SARB referrals. For example, if the reason for absences is related to illness, the school nurse could gather information prior to the SARB meeting.

Although stakeholders supported the establishment of an illness code, the Business Services department, which has the ability to create a specific illness code, indicated that the current code (Code 1) already captures this data, despite the fact that other reasons for absence are included in the code. Retrospectively, a representative from Business Services should have been included as a stakeholder because the rationale for establishing an illness code would have been communicated.

During the project, site administrators referred two students with severe illness chronic absences to the school nurse and involved the school nurse in Student Attendance Review Team (SART) meetings to address chronic absences. SART is a school site intervention to formally address barriers to regular attendance. The health clerk alerted the school nurse regarding four students with high absenteeism rates, and those who had frequent health office visits. Since the school nurse is assigned multiple school sites, the health clerk is more familiar with students and their life circumstances. Attendance clerks referred two students and presented the school nurse with medical notes, which excused the absences. The background information provided by school administrators, the health clerk, and attendance clerks contributed to a more comprehensive history of the need for referral.

Practices of Other Districts

Assessment of the attendance tracking practices of four other districts indicated that it is feasible to establish a specific illness code and develop a school nurse referral

process. A lead nurse from one district reported that their district established a referral process, in which attendance clerks notified the school nurse when a student is chronically absent due to illness. This process facilitates a multidisciplinary effort to mitigate future absences through attendance monitoring of at-risk students and the school nurse investigating the reason for the chronic absences. According to a Baltimore school nurse, their district utilized additional illness coding options (i.e., asthma, flu, cold, and other common ailments). However, it was reported that accurate documentation of the reason for the absence is challenging because families often do not provide more information beyond "sick" as a reason for the absence. Another challenge for the Baltimore district is the lack of adequate training provided to those coding the absences to ensure that they use appropriate coding options when recording an absence. Representatives from two California districts reported that school nurses are integrated into their efforts to curtail chronic absenteeism. One district recently implemented this process and will be collecting data to determine if the incorporation of a school nurse intervention affects the rate of chronic absence.

As part of the Focus phase, the author attended a national school-based health conference in Southern California on best-practice attendance strategies. At the conference, two southern California districts reported that one of their strategies in addressing chronic absences is the inclusion of the school nurse in the attendance process, which may include conducting home visits. The Director of Attendance Works (2015), a national and state initiative with a mission to advance student success and reduce equity gaps by reducing chronic absence, identified three tiers of intervention to reduce chronic absence. Tier 1 is prevention oriented and is for all students with good attendance. At

the conference, a district-provided examples of Tier 1 interventions, including updating attendance related board policies, developing strong data systems that accurately captures attendance information, and promoting committed district staff who support attendance efforts. Tier 2 interventions focus on students who have a past history of moderate chronic absence (missing 10% or more of school days) or who have a risk factor (i.e., chronic illness) and require more individualized support. Another district reported adding a health intervention to their Tier 2 process to prevent increased absence due to chronic illness. The school nurse identified students and developed specific plans for the health intervention. Tier 3 strategies are designed for students who missed 20% or more school days or face a risk factor, such as involvement with the juvenile justice system, homelessness, or has an incarcerated parent. Tier 3 strategies include initiating referrals to community resources (i.e., social services, counseling or housing), a referral to SARB, and collaborating with the Court system to link the student to additional services or programs that would assist with overcoming barriers to attendance.

Analyze

In the second phase of the FADE model, data is collected and analyzed to establish baselines and identify root causes (Duke University School of Medicine, 2016). An Excel attendance report generated on March 2, 2018, identified 117 ninth and tenth grade students with moderate to severe chronic absence. This dataset was analyzed to determine the number of students with chronic absence due to illness, whether these absences occurred in clusters, and the academic outcomes in the first semester. Table 2 shows attendance categories for the project school from 2015 through March 2018.

Table 2.

District Attendance Data for School Years 2015-2016, 2016-2017, and Partial 2017-2018. Retrieved 3/29/18.

District Attendance by Grade by Year - High (Grade 9-12)											
Selected School: 755									Today: 3/29/2018		
GRADE	NUMBER severe chronic absence	PERCENT severe chronic absence	NUMBER moderate chronic absence	PERCENT moderate chronic absence	NUMBER ALL chronic absence (severe + moderate)	PERCENT ALL chronic absence (severe + moderate)	NUMBER at-risk attendance	PERCENT at-risk attendance	NUMBER satisfactory attendance	PERCENT satisfactory attendance	Total Students
2017 - 2018											
Grade 9	21	1.7%	60	4.8%	81	6.4%	171	13.6%	1,008	80.0%	1,260
Grade 10	22	1.9%	47	4.1%	69	6.0%	185	16.2%	887	77.7%	1,141
Grade 11	19	1.7%	63	5.5%	82	7.2%	204	17.9%	853	74.9%	1,139
Grade 12	24	2.3%	84	8.2%	108	10.5%	223	21.7%	696	67.8%	1,027
Totals	86	1.9%	254	5.6%	340	7.4%	783	17.1%	3,444	75.4%	4,567
2016 - 2017											
Grade 9	9	0.8%	45	3.9%	54	4.7%	162	14.0%	939	81.3%	1,155
Grade 10	25	2.1%	63	5.4%	88	7.6%	188	16.1%	889	76.3%	1,165
Grade 11	23	2.1%	64	5.9%	87	8.0%	191	17.6%	808	74.4%	1,086
Grade 12	17	1.7%	106	10.9%	123	12.6%	254	26.1%	598	61.3%	975
Totals	74	1.7%	278	6.3%	352	8.0%	795	18.1%	3,234	73.8%	4,381
2015 - 2016											
Grade 9	15	1.2%	58	4.8%	73	6.1%	159	13.2%	970	80.7%	1,202
Grade 10	19	1.7%	70	6.2%	89	7.9%	184	16.3%	854	75.8%	1,127
Grade 11	20	1.9%	72	7.0%	92	8.9%	176	17.1%	764	74.0%	1,032
Grade 12	15	1.7%	86	9.5%	101	11.2%	214	23.7%	587	65.1%	902
Totals	69	1.6%	286	6.7%	355	8.3%	733	17.2%	3,175	74.5%	4,263

DEFINITIONS:

Severe chronic absence: Missing 20% or more of total school days

Moderate chronic absence: Missing 10 -19.99% of total school days

ALL chronic absence: Missing 10% or more school days (sums moderate + severe chronic)

At-risk attendance: Missing 5-9.99% of total school days

Satisfactory attendance: Missing less than 5% of total school days

Illness Related Chronic Absence (IRCA)

The attendance histories of the 117 9th and 10th grade students with chronic absences were reviewed to determine if an illness was the reason for the absence. Illness absence was defined as missing a full school day due to a reported illness or health related appointment (i.e., doctor's visit, mental health, or dental). The criterion for illness chronic absences was met when 51% or more of absences were reported as health related. The frequency of absences related to illness is shown in Table 3. Among ninth graders with moderate chronic absences, 71% of those absences were reported as illness-related, and for tenth graders, the rate was slightly higher, 73%. Of those who met the severe chronic absence category, 46% of ninth graders and 38% of tenth graders missed school due to reported illness. Of the 117 students in the 9th and 10th grade with moderate to severe chronic absences, 66% reported illness as the primary reason for the absences.

Table 3.

Students with Moderate to Severe Chronic Absences

Grade	Moderate CA N	Moderate IRCA N (%)	Severe CA N	Severe IRCA N (%)	Total Moderate and Severe CA N	Total Moderate and Severe IRCA N (%)
9	42	30 (71)	13	6 (46)	55	36 (65)
10	49	36 (73)	13	5 (38)	62	41 (66)
Total	91	66 (73)	26	11(42)	117	77 (66)

Note: CA = Chronic Absence. IRCA = Illness Related Chronic Absence.

Clustered Illness Related Chronic Absence (CIRCA)

A clustered illness related chronic absence is defined as four or more consecutive missed school days due to an illness related reason. Review of the attendance history of

77 students with moderate to severe illness related chronic absences identified that 34% of these students met the criteria for CIRCA. Comparison of the moderate and severe chronic illness categories showed that students in the severe illness related chronic absences category had a higher proportionate of clustered absences as shown in Table 4. Of students with clustered absence, 54% were male, 62% were tenth graders, and 43% had a chronic health condition. Of the six students with asthma, 50% had a prescribed inhaler available at school.

Table 4.

Students with Clustered Illness Related Chronic Absences

Grade	Moderate IRCA N	Moderate IRCA N (%)	Severe CIRCA N	Severe CIRCA N (%)	Total Moderate and Severe IRCA N	Total Moderate and Severe CIRCA N (%)
9	30	7 (23)	6	3 (50)	36	10 (28)
10	36	12 (33)	5	4 (80)	41	16 (39)
Total	66	19 (29)	11	7 (64)	77	26 (34)

Note: IRCA=Illness Related Chronic Absence. CIRCA=Clustered Illness Related Chronic Absences.

Clustered absences, especially when they occur periodically, may be indicative of serious health concerns. Only three of the 27 students were referred to the school nurse for assessment and intervention. A SART contract did not improve a student's attendance, and at the SARB hearing, the decision was to enroll the student in on-line classes until the treatment regimen is completed. Another student had increasing challenges with her physical and mental health. Homebound instruction was the most suitable placement for her.

Academic Outcomes

Of 30 ninth graders with moderate IRCA, 10% failed one or more courses and teachers reported that excessive absences affected academic progress in 17% of these students. In comparison, 17% of students with severe IRCA failed one or more courses due to excessive absences. Of 77 ninth and tenth grade students, 14% failed one or more courses in the first semester.

Students with CIRCA had even poorer academic outcomes: 40% of ninth graders and 44% of tenth graders failed at least one class in the first semester. Failed courses translate into credit deficiency which increases the risk of not meeting high school graduation requirements.

Table 5.

Academic Outcome of Illness Chronic Absences

Grade	Moderate Chronic Illness Absence N = 66			Severe Chronic Illness Absence N = 11		
	N	Failed ≥ 1 Class N (%)	Excessive Absences Affected Progress N (%)	N	Failed ≥ 1 Class N (%)	Excessive Absences Affected Progress N (%)
9	30	3 (10)	5 (17)	6	1 (17)	1 (17)
10	36	4 (11)	7 (19)	5	3 (60)	4 (80)
Total	66	7 (11)	12 (18)	11	4 (36)	5 (45)

Note: The failed course(s) occurred during the first semester of the current school year. Of 77 students with moderate to severe illness chronic absences, 14% failed one or more courses in the first semester.

Case Study Selection Process

A review process (Figure 4) was used to select students who missed four or more consecutive school days due to illness, i.e., clustered illness absence, as these students might have health conditions amenable to nursing intervention. Of the 117 students who

met the moderate to severe absence threshold, 77 students met the criteria for IRCA and 26 students had CIRCA. These 26 students' records were examined for the student's attendance and health history, course grades, the frequency of health office visits, contact with parents, visit notes, enrollment date, programs that the student is enrolled in (i.e., Special Education, Section 504 Plan), and if SART/SARB meetings had been held. Planned individualized nursing interventions are included in the case studies.

Figure 2. Case study subject selection process.

Case 1. A 14-year old ninth grade male student has a history of chronic absenteeism since 2014. Due to attendance issues, a SART contract was completed for the student in 2014 and 2016, and a SARB hearing was held in 2016. However, these interventions did not improve attendance. In the current school year, he missed 23 days,

and 95% of these absences were reportedly illness-related. The student was diagnosed with asthma in 2014. The parent reported that an inhaler is available at home. However, one has not been provided for use during the school day. Asthma was not specifically cited as the reason for the absences. Although most of the absences were illness-related, a school nurse referral was not made. He had an episode of clustered absences (missed four consecutive days) in October 2017. He was reportedly ill, but a specific reason for the absence was not documented. The student had one health office visit due to nausea. Teachers cited that excessive absences affected progress, indicating that he has potential for better academic performance. He passed all his courses, earning two Ds, because he was able to submit make-up work.

Table 6

Case 1: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity and school performance and poor attendance.	<p>Identify the level asthma severity by obtaining medical verification of diagnosis.</p> <p>In collaboration with the healthcare provider, develop an asthma action plan.</p> <p>Assess the student and parent's knowledge deficit related to asthma and self-care management. Provide education.</p> <p>Obtain medication authorization form and asthma management supplies.</p>	<p>The student will</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.

Case 2. The parent of a 14-year old ninth female grader reported the student has a history of anxiety/depression, but no onset date was provided. The parent also reported that the student is being evaluated for an immune system issue. Medical verification and treatment plan for both conditions is lacking. The student missed 23 school days, and all the absences were reportedly due to illness. There were no health office visits during this school year. The school nurse was not notified of the three episodes of clustered absences in the first semester. A SART meeting was not initiated. The school counselor and parent decided to transition the student to an on-line school because the student's mental health and immune system issues reportedly were barriers to school attendance. The alternative academic placement enabled her to earn credits for all her fall courses. The plan is to transition her back to the high school campus in the upcoming school year.

Table 7

Case 2: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective individual coping related to lack of or inadequate coping strategies.	Obtain a release of medical information from parent.	The student will increase her knowledge about anxiety disorder and her anxiety management plan.
	Contact the medical provider to verify diagnosis and treatment plan.	
	Encourage medical management and scheduling of medical appointments outside of school hours and during school breaks.	The student will miss less than 10% of school days evidenced by school records.
Deficient knowledge related to lack of knowledge of specific immunodeficiency disease.	Obtain signed release of information from parent in order to facilitate communication and collaboration with	The student will describe signs and symptoms of infection in a pretest and posttest.

student's healthcare providers regarding student's health status and needs in the school setting.

Case 3. A 14-year old ninth grader female who missed 20 school days received A's and B's in all her courses in the first semester, but the 13 missed days in the second semester affected academic achievement. There is no history of a SART referral. Ninety percent of the absences were reported to be illness related. However, eczema is the only medical condition noted on records. The student had no documented health office visits or medication authorizations on file. A medical note excused the clustered nine-day absence, but the school nurse was not notified. This absence at the beginning of the second semester may have placed the student at risk of failing four of six classes. Progress notes from teachers stated that the student had excessive absences and missing/incomplete work. The parent(s) did not contact the school to arrange accommodations to assist the student in catching up with missed work.

Table 8

Case 3: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity and school performance and poor attendance.	Contact parent to determine student's health status and access to medical care. Obtain a signed release of information from the parent in order to facilitate communication and collaboration with student's healthcare providers regarding	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.

student's health status and
needs in the school setting.

Case 4. A 15-year old female in ninth grade, with no history of a SART referral, missed 20 school days and 75% of those absences were attributed to illness. There was no report of a diagnosed health condition. The student had three health office visits during the current school year due to stomachache and cold symptoms). The twelve school days missed, with a 10 day clustered absence, in the month of October may have contributed to failing three classes. Teachers reported the student had missing/incomplete homework and performed poorly on tests, projects, and/or assignments. The student will need to repeat the failed courses during the summer for high school credit recovery.

Table 9

Case 4: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity and school performance and poor attendance.	Contact parent to determine student's health status and access to medical care. Consult with the student's academic counselor regarding student's attendance, frequency of health visits, lack of medical verification, and risk for drop out. Develop a plan to mitigate chronic absence.	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.
Health-seeking behavior related to somatic complaints	Negotiate with the student to limit health office visits that interfere with classroom attendance, limiting visits to before school, during break or	Decrease frequency of visits to the health office.

lunch time, or after school
as appropriate, unless
emergency situation.

Case 5. A 14-year old male student missed 17 days of school, and 65% were illness-related absences. Although medical notes were provided for the two clustered illness-related absences, a medical diagnosis was not provided. Review of health office visits indicated the student had been to the health office four times during the current school year due to psychosomatic complaints (i.e., headaches, stomachaches, and sore throat). There was no prescribed medication authorized for school use. The student failed two courses in the first semester, and “excessive absences” affected academic progress.

10

Case 5: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to poor attendance.	Contact parent to determine student’s health status and access to medical care. Consult with the student’s academic counselor regarding student’s attendance, frequency of health visits, lack of medical verification regarding chronic illness absences, and risk for drop out. Develop a plan to mitigate chronic absence.	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.
Health-seeking behavior related to somatic complaints	Negotiate with the student to limit health office visits that interfere with classroom attendance, limiting visits to before school, during break or	Decrease frequency of visits to the health office.

lunch time, or after school as appropriate, unless emergency situation.

Recognize and praise the student's efforts to adopt and maintain appropriate coping mechanisms.

Case 6. A 14-year old ninth grader missed 15 days of school. Although there was no reported health condition, 93% of those absences were health related. There is no history of a SART referral. The parent reported the student sustained an injury in the second semester that resulted in a five day clustered absence. Two health office visits during the current school year were due to an abrasion and a vomiting episode. The student passed all his first semester classes. The quarter progress report in the second semester indicated he is in danger of failing three classes, and it may be related to the clustered absence. Teachers commented that excessive absences have affected academic progress, and that he had missing or incomplete work.

Table 11

Case 6: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity and school performance and poor attendance.	Contact parent to determine student's health status, reasons for absences, and access to medical care. Refer to community resources as needed.	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.

Case 7. A 14-year old female tenth grade student with a history of chronic absence missed 13 school days during the current school year. The SART meeting in

2015 did not curtail chronic absence. Twelve of the 13 days missed school days were related to a diagnosed heart defect. The parent reported that most of the absences were due to medical appointments outside of the county. The school nurse recommended transitioning medical care to a closer facility. The parent reported there was a lapse in insurance coverage. The school nurse provided assistance with access to medical care by referring the family to community resources. The student presented to the health office twice during the school year due to tachycardia. An emergency care plan was developed. The student, parent, and staff were trained on how to respond appropriately when the student has a cardiac related episode during the school day. The student failed one class in the first semester.

Table 12

Case 7: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Deficient knowledge related to disease self-management.	Obtain a signed release of information from the parent in order to facilitate communication and collaboration with student's healthcare providers regarding student's health status and academic progress due to missed school days.	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to medical appointments.
	Educate student about her medical condition and teach self-management interventions.	The student will describe signs and symptoms of tachycardia in a pretest and posttest. The student will demonstrate strategies to manage tachycardia episodes.

Case 8. A 15-year old ninth grade female student missed 43 days of the school year. There is no history of a SART referral. The parent provided a medical note, excusing a 16-day clustered absence that indicated that student was undergoing evaluation. No information was provided regarding a probable diagnosis or medical evaluation plan. The student had three health office visits (for a bandage, cold symptoms, and nausea) during the current school year. An application for homebound instruction was approved without input from the school nurse. The courses offered in the homebound instruction curriculum do not meet college admission requirements.

Table 13

Case 8: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Risk for impaired social interaction related to homebound placement resulting in limited opportunities for age-appropriate social interaction.	<p>Follow up on the results of medical tests and make appropriate return to school plan. Develop a health plan as needed.</p> <p>Encourage parent to facilitate peer engagement while student is on homebound instruction.</p> <p>Encourage student to regularly contact peers.</p>	Maintain interactions with peers and develop age-appropriate relationships.

Case 9. A 14-year old male ninth grader in Special Education missed 35 days this school year. There is no history of a SART referral. The student reportedly has diagnosis of absence seizure, asthma, and autism. An inhaler was not prescribed for use at school, and the student did not have asthma related health office visits. Twenty-five of

the 35 missed days were illness-related. The parent did not report the specific reasons for the illness absences, including the two cluster episodes in November and February. A referral to the school nurse was lacking.

Table 14

Case 9: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Deficient knowledge related to chronic illness diagnosis.	<p data-bbox="678 627 1036 737">Contact parent to determine student's health status and access to medical care.</p> <p data-bbox="678 779 1036 1104">Obtain a signed release of information from the parent in order to facilitate communication and collaboration with student's healthcare providers regarding student's health status and needs in the school setting.</p> <p data-bbox="678 1146 1036 1283">Develop a health plan based on medical information obtained from the healthcare provider.</p> <p data-bbox="678 1325 1036 1461">Educate parent regarding determining when to keep student at home due to illness.</p> <p data-bbox="678 1503 1036 1719">Communicate with the IEP team regarding concern about student's chronic absence. IEP team to develop a goal to mitigate chronic absence.</p>	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.

Case 10. A 15-year old female missed 26 missed school days. There is no history of a SART referral. Although 21 days were excused as an illness absence, the parent did not report any diagnosed health conditions. From September 2017 to January 2018, the student missed between three to four days per month, with a five day clustered absence in January. Three health office visits during the school year were due to back pain, abrasion, and nausea. The student failed two classes in the first semester, and the teachers of those classes reported that excessive absences affected progress. She also had missing or incomplete class work. The student is currently in danger of failing two additional courses that places her at risk for not graduating.

Table 15

Case 10: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity and school performance and poor attendance.	Contact parent to determine student's health status, reasons for absences, and access to medical care. Refer to community resources as needed. Consult with the student's academic counselor regarding student's attendance, lack of medical verification regarding chronic illness absences, and risk for drop out. Develop a plan to mitigate chronic absence.	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.

Case 11. A 16-year old female tenth grader, classified as non-severely handicapped, missed 22 school days. There is no history of a SART referral. The

student is diagnosed with Down Syndrome, hydronephrosis, and hypothyroidism. Of the 22 missed days, and 77% were excused as illness absences. A referral for school nurse intervention was not made although clustered absences occurred in August and October 2017. A medical note to excuse absences was not received.

Table 16.

Case 11: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Deficient knowledge related to chronic illness diagnosis.	<p>Contact parent to determine student's health status and access to medical care.</p> <p>Obtain a signed release of information from the parent in order to facilitate communication and collaboration with student's healthcare providers regarding student's health status and needs in the school setting.</p> <p>Develop a health plan based on medical information obtained from the healthcare provider.</p> <p>Educate parent regarding determining when to keep student at home due to illness.</p> <p>Communicate with the IEP team regarding concern about student's chronic absence. IEP team to develop a goal to mitigate chronic absence.</p>	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.

Case 12. A 16-year old tenth grader received A's and B's in the first semester. However, a 10-day clustered absence in the second semester placed her at risk of failing courses. There is no history of prior attendance issues. Medical diagnoses include asthma and migraines. The student has demonstrated ability to self-manage asthma symptoms as evidenced by no asthma related health office visits. An inhaler is prescribed for school use. The parent reported that migraines have intensified in the second semester, resulting in increased absences. Propranolol and Zofran have been ineffective in controlling migraine symptoms. She is undergoing a medical evaluation to investigate the cause of migraines. The parent consulted with the homebound instruction team regarding temporarily placing the student in the program until migraine symptoms are manageable. The team explained to the parent that courses offered in the program do not meet college admission requirements. The parent opted to place the student in an on-line program.

Table 17

Case 12: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective therapeutic migraine regimen management related to knowledge deficit.	Assess the student and family's knowledge of migraines and provide education. Obtain a signed release of information to obtain pertinent medical orders and records and to share information with the medical provider. With family and medical provider input, assemble a	The student will 1. Miss less than 10% of school days due to illness. 2. Select appropriate comfort measures prior to exacerbation of migraine.

list of comfort measures and help student select appropriate choice based on level of discomfort. Incorporate these measures in a health plan.

Case 13. A 16-year old tenth grader with asthma had sporadic days of illness absences. The 16 missed school days were reported to be illness related. On average this school year, the student has missed about two days per month. The specific reason was not given for a four-day clustered absence at the end of August 2017. The student has not used the prescribed quick-relief inhaler. There were no health office visits during this school year.

Table 18

Case 13: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Deficient knowledge related to chronic illness diagnosis.	<p>Contact parent to determine student's health status and access to medical care.</p> <p>Obtain a signed release of information from the parent in order to facilitate communication and collaboration with student's healthcare providers regarding student's health status and needs in the school setting.</p> <p>Develop a health plan based on medical information obtained from the healthcare provider.</p>	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.

Educate parent regarding determining when to keep student at home due to illness.

Case 14. A 15-year old tenth grader with no history of a SART referral missed 15 days of school. Although there is no documented health condition, the absences were attributed to illness. A four-day clustered absence occurred in September 2017. On the one health office visit this school year, the student reported she has reflux. The student failed two courses in the first semester and is in danger of failing five classes in the second semester. A teacher reported that excessive absences affected academic progress.

Table 19

Case 14: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease school performance and poor attendance.	Contact parent to determine student's health status, reason for chronic absence, and access to medical care. Refer to community resources as needed. Develop a health plan if needed.	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.
	Educate parent regarding determining when to keep student at home due to illness.	
	Request that the attendance clerks notify the school nurse if illness absences continue.	

Case 15. A 16-year old tenth grade missed 14 school days, with a four-day clustered absence in October 2017. There is no history of a SART referral. Eleven absences were reportedly illness-related, but there is no parent report of a health condition. There is no recorded health office visit during the current school year. The student failed four courses in the first semester. Teachers reported that excessive absences affected academic progress.

Table 20

Case 15: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity and school performance, and poor attendance.	<p>Contact parent to determine student's health status, reason for chronic absence, and access to medical care. Refer to community resources as needed. Develop a health plan if needed.</p> <p>Educate parent regarding determining when to keep student at home due to illness.</p> <p>Request that the attendance clerks notify the school nurse if illness absences continue.</p> <p>Inform the school counselor regarding the impact of student's poor attendance on academic performance.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.

Case 16. A 15-year old male student missed 14 days this school year. There is no history of a SART referral. Thirteen absences were reported as illness related. A five-day clustered absence occurred in February 2018, yet a school nurse referral was not made. Other than a sustained hairline fracture in October 2017, there is no record of a diagnosed health condition. The student had two health office visits this school year (one related to the leg injury and another for nausea). He passed all courses in the first semester, but he is currently failing three classes. Teacher comments include “excessive absences affect progress” and “missing/incomplete class work”.

Table 21

Case 16: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity and school performance, and poor attendance.	<p>Contact parent to determine student’s health status, reason for chronic absence, and access to medical care. Refer to community resources as needed. Develop a health plan if needed.</p> <p>Educate parent regarding determining when to keep student at home due to illness.</p> <p>Request that the attendance clerks notify the school nurse if illness absences continue.</p> <p>Inform the school counselor regarding the impact of student’s poor attendance on academic performance.</p>	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.

Case 17. A 15-year missed 14 school days in the school year, of which 13 were illness absences. There is no history of a SART referral. A medical note did not specifically explain the reason for a five day clustered absence in September 2017. Four health office visits were recorded for the school year. Reasons for the visits include cramps, nausea, vomiting, and stomachache. There is no medical diagnosis on file. She passed all her courses in the first semester.

Table 22

Case 17: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Knowledge deficit related to impact of chronic absenteeism on academic achievement.	Assess the reason for chronic absenteeism and barriers to good attendance.	The student and parent will verbalize understanding of appropriate reasons for an illness absence.
	Link the student and family to resources as needed (i.e., medical coverage).	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.
	Educate parent and student about appropriate health reasons for missing school.	

Case 18. A 15-year old tenth grader missed 12 school days, of which 10 were attributed to illness. A four day clustered absence in November 2017 was due to an appendectomy. Nine health office visits during the school year were due to cramps, stomachache, headache, and vomiting. A review of the student's health record revealed that she failed vision screen (20/100+) two years ago. The school nurse scheduled a vision re-screen to determine if the student had an optometry evaluation. Teachers

reported that the student had missing or incomplete homework, and performed poorly on tests. She is deficient by 45 credits, placing her at high risk for high school drop out.

Table 23

Case 18: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity and school performance, and poor attendance.	Meet with the parent and student to assess the reason for chronic absence and academic underperformance.	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.
	Consult with the academic advisor and teachers regarding possible need for academic support.	The student will demonstrate motivation to learn by seeking academic support as needed.
	Initiate a SART referral to address chronic absence and academic risk.	

Case 19. A 15-year old tenth grade student missed 12 school days during this school year, seven of which were illness related. The other five missed days were coded as trancies. There is no history of a SART referral. A four day clustered absence in November 2017 was due to a leg injury. There is no other health concern. He had one health visit due to an injury he sustained when he punched a wall. He failed two courses in the first semester, and is currently at risk of failing four. Multiple teachers reported that he had missing or incomplete class work.

Table 24

Case 19: Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity and school performance, and poor attendance.	Meet with the parent and student to assess the reason for chronic absence and academic underperformance.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness. 2. The student will demonstrate motivation

	Consult with the academic advisor and teachers regarding possible need for academic support.	to learn by seeking academic support as needed.
	Consult with an administrator regarding truancies.	
	Initiate a SART referral to address chronic absence and academic risk.	
Risk for injury due to lack of coping strategies.	Refer to school counselor regarding possible anger management.	The student will demonstrate effective coping strategies when he is angry.

Case 20. A 15-year old tenth grader missed 12 school days at the beginning of the current school year due to being hospitalized for pneumonia. He does not have a history of chronic absence and has strong academic achievement. He has not been absent since that time. The recommendation for a situation like this is to educate the attendance clerks to refer illness related clustered absences for school nurse assessment and intervention.

Case 21. A 16-year old tenth grader enrolled at the beginning of the second semester. Of the 31 days enrolled, he missed four days of school due to the flu. His absences affected academic progress. A review of health records from the previous district indicated he failed the near and distance vision screen with a 20/100+ results. The school nurse scheduled a vision re-screen. There is no report of any other health concern. Limited information is available from the previous district's records.

Table 25

Case 21. Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Risk for ineffective role performance of educational attainment related to limitation of vision deficit.	<p>Conduct a vision screen to determine visual acuity and if financial assistance is needed to obtain an exam and glasses.</p> <p>Contact parent to assess the student's health and academic history.</p>	The student will describe how vision deficit affect the ability to learn.

Case 22. A 16-year old tenth grade student enrolled in the district at the beginning of the second semester. Of the 21 days since enrollment, a medical note excused a four day clustered absence, but a specific reason was not provided. The parent reported that the student was diagnosed with asthma, but an inhaler was not provided for asthma management in school. He did not have any health office visits. He is at risk of failing two courses. The math teacher reported that excessive absences affected progress. Other teachers reported that the student had missing or incomplete homework. The health file from the previous district contains scant information.

Table 26

Case 22. Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Deficient knowledge about asthma and self-care.	<p>Contact the parent to assess asthma severity and discuss the treatment plan.</p> <p>Obtain a medication authorization form for a quick relief inhaler.</p>	The parent will provide a medical authorization to allow the use of a quick relief inhaler.

Assess the student's developmental and emotional readiness for self-carrying of quick-relief medication.	The student will demonstrate asthma self-management competency.
Provide asthma education to parent and student based on their level of understanding of the disease process and treatment.	

Case 23. A 15-year old tenth grade female has missed 66 days of school, and 42 days were reportedly due to a chronic pain condition. At the initial meeting, an administrator and the nurse discussed concerns related to poor attendance and academic progress. The parent reported that the pain episodes had increased in frequency and intensity, causing limited activity tolerance. The nurse requested verification of the medical condition and the treatment plan. Alternative education placement to prevent hindrance to academic progression was recommended at the meeting, such as homebound instruction. However, the parent declined the recommendations. After the parent provided a medical note validating the diagnosis, absences increased and prompted the initiation of the SART process. At the SART meeting, the parent was informed that if attendance does not improve, a referral to the SARB would be initiated unless a medical note clearly indicates the expected frequency of missed school days and identifies the treatment plan. Alternative education options were discussed, but the parent declined the options. The nurse contacted the medical provider to relay concerns regarding attendance and academic progress as well as recommendations for alternative education placements. The medical office personnel stated that children with a similar diagnosis are often placed

on homebound instruction when pain levels are unmanageable. The nurse requested that the medical provider discuss establishing homebound instruction at an upcoming visit. Excessive absences resulted in two failed classes in the first semester due to incomplete homework and poor performance on tests. The case was referred to SARB and alternative education placement options were presented to the parent and student. Homebound instruction was refused because the curriculum does not meet college requirements. On-line learning is being considered as an alternative education placement option.

Table 27

Case 23. Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Nursing Interventions	Expected Outcomes
Anticipatory Guidance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assist student identify possible effects of failing classes. • Anxiety reduction associated with pain and/or academic challenges. 	The student will verbalize effective coping strategies for stressful situations.
Chronic Pain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtain a medication authorization form to manage pain as needed. • Establish systematic tracking of pain. Ask student to maintain a diary of pain ratings, timing, precipitating events, and best intervention to relieve pain. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The student's chronic pain will be controlled at least 80% of the time • The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to health condition.

Case 24. A severely chronic absent 17-year old tenth grader had a ten day clustered absence due to complications of kidney failure. She missed 44 days of school, and 21 were illness related absences. The school nurse developed a health plan for the student at the beginning of the school year. Five health office visits during this school

year were due to headaches and vomiting. She was placed on homebound instruction at the end of the first semester status post kidney transplant. The parent reported that the student gained weight due to side effects of prescribed medications. She also reported that the student stays in her room and has limited interaction with peers. The nurse was not notified when the student returned to school in the second semester. The student would have benefitted from a hospital to school transition plan to assess and provide supports the student may need upon return to school. The student is struggling academically as evidenced by a 25-unit credit deficiency.

Table 28

Case 24. Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Disturbed body image due to weight gain as a result of side effects of medication regiment.	<p>Assess student's concerns related to weight gain.</p> <p>Refer the student to the school counselor for possible depression or anxiety.</p> <p>Recommend that the parent schedule a mental health evaluation to rule out depression and anxiety, and to obtain support if needed.</p>	<p>The student will</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incorporate body changes into self-concept without negating self-esteem. 2. Demonstrate ability to create and maintain social relationships with peers and adults.

Case 25. A 16-year old tenth grader missed 35 days of school, and 26 days were illness related absences. Six of the illness related absences were due to medical appointments. A medical note, which did not specify the reason for the absence, excused a five day clustered absence. The student had one health office visit due to a reported vomiting episode. The student has not needed the inhaler prescribed for asthma

management during school hours. The school nurse requested that the attendance clerks refer future illness absences for school nurse intervention. She failed one course in the fall semester, and is in danger of failing four courses in the second semester. Teachers reported that excessive absences affected progress.

Table 29

Case 25. Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity and school performance and poor attendance.	<p>Meet with the parent and student to assess the reason for chronic absence and academic underperformance.</p> <p>Consult with the academic advisor and teachers regarding possible need for academic support.</p> <p>Consult with an administrator regarding truancies.</p> <p>Initiate a SART referral to address chronic absence and academic risk.</p>	<p>The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness.</p> <p>Medical appointments will be scheduled after school or during a non-school day.</p>

Case 26. A 15-year old tenth grader missed 33 school days. Although the student does not have a diagnosed health condition, 29 days were reported as illness related absences. A SART meeting occurred in 2016. There were no recorded health office visits during this school year. The student failed three courses in the first semester, and is credit deficient by 40 units. Teachers reported that excessive absences affected academic progress.

Table 30

Case 26. Nursing diagnosis, interventions and expected outcomes.

Nursing Diagnosis	Interventions	Outcomes
Ineffective role performance related to decrease productivity, and school performance and poor attendance.	<p>Meet with the parent and student to assess the reason for chronic absence and academic underperformance.</p> <p>Consult with the academic advisor and teachers regarding need for academic support and credit recovery.</p> <p>Consult with an administrator regarding truancies.</p> <p>Initiate a SART referral to address chronic absence and academic risk.</p>	The student will miss less than 10% of school days due to illness, resulting in improved academic trajectory.

Case Study Summary

Insights drawn from analysis of the CIRCA in the 26 students include:

- There is inconsistent practice in the documentation of the reason for an illness absence. Some attendance clerks documented when medical verification was received or if it was per parent report. Some documented the reason for the illness absence. Others simply coded the absence as a 1, an unexcused absence, and noted in the narrative the student was ill.
- 62% of the students with CIRCA are in the tenth grade.
- 45% of the students with CIRCA have a diagnosed chronic health condition.
- Chronic absence affected academic progress in most of the students.

- Of 26 students with CIRCA, only two were referred to the school nurse.

Referring cases to the school nurse was not a common practice, and may be due to lack of awareness that the school nurse has a role in addressing chronic absenteeism. Since 66% of the 117 students with moderate to severe chronic absences from August-March 2018, reported illness as the reason for the absence, involving the school nurse in the Tier 2 Response to Intervention (RTI) process may prevent worsening attendance. Tier 2 comprises students who have a history of missing at least 10% of school days or who have a risk factor (i.e., chronic illness), which may make school attendance a challenge. Students in Tier 2 require more individualized support. Therefore, students whose chronic illness affects attendance may benefit from school nurse care coordination efforts.

DISCUSSION

Evidence suggests that attendance and course performance in the ninth grade are highly predictive of high school dropout (Allensworth, Gwynne, Moore, de La Torre, & University of Chicago, 2014). Students with a chronic health condition have a higher incidence of absences and poor educational attainment (Champaloux et al., 2015; Crump et al., 2013). Emerson et al. (2016) reported that the parents of children with chronic illness might extend absences due to an increased perception of vulnerability in their child. Since illness was the most common reason for absences in the 117 students who met the moderate to severe absence criteria, a specific illness code is a simple method of identifying and tracking students with illness chronic absence. Rodriguez et al. (2014) concluded that school nurses have a key role in lowering absenteeism rates and emergency room visits in students with asthma. If students are at risk for chronic absenteeism due to illness, involving the school nurse as part of a Tier 2 intervention may potentially prevent worsening attendance and consequently poor academic outcomes. The school nurse is in a position to inquire about health reasons for absences and engage in care coordination efforts to improve school attendance.

Develop

In the Develop phase, a solution to the problem and a plan for implementation are formulated (Barton, Danek, Johns, & Coons, 1998). Review of district practices, attendance data, information gleaned from other district practices and case review results culminated in the development of deliverables that may facilitate an improved process of identifying students at risk of illness-related chronic absences prior to the negative consequences of academic performance. The deliverables included a school nurse

referral process with an accompanying algorithm, a chronic absence district policy, a chronic illness verification form, and pilot project proposal.

Several barriers posed challenges in implementing the proposed pilot project. The Execute and Evaluate stages of FADE will be discussed in the Conclusion and Recommendations section.

Non-inclusion of a key stakeholder. The participation of the Business Services administrator was critical in establishing an illness code because the department has the ability to approve it. The lack of a specific illness code deterred the implementation of the pilot action plan of identifying students at risk for academic underachievement due to illness-related chronic absenteeism.

Lack of specific illness code. The department with the decision-making ability to approve an illness code did not see the necessity for it, citing that the excused absence Code 1 encompasses the illness absences. However, identifying the reason for an absence is a tedious task because a Code 1 excused absence could be due to illness or injury, appointments (medical, dental, optometric, psychological, or chiropractic), funeral services of immediate family member, jury duty, quarantine, or a teen parent caring for a sick child. A Code 2 excused absence includes court appearance/probation/legal appointment/investigative hearing, religious holiday, ceremony or retreat, employment conference, funeral service other than that of an immediate family member, personal reasons requested by a parent or guardian-approved by Administrator or Administrative Designee. In addition, there is no system feature to aggregate students with a specific absence code and thus each day must be reviewed to identify students absent due to illness.

Lack of standard process. There is a lack of standardization in the documentation of the reason for absences. For example, an attendance clerk may specify the reason for the absence in the narrative section, such as illness or a dental appointment, while another clerk may feel that coding the absence with a “1” is sufficient since it is deemed excused. Another barrier is the attendance clerk’s uncertainty about asking for the reason for the absence. For example, an attendance clerk stated she believed she could not ask the parent to specify the reason for the illness absence.

Chronic absences are first noticed when a student is at risk of failing a class(es), which may be too late in the semester for the student to improve grades. The school nurse is often unaware of students who have excessive illness absences since a process to identify these absences is lacking. Therefore, a school nurse referral and subsequent intervention cannot be initiated.

Action plan revision. Following identification of barriers to action plan implementation led to development of a revised action plan. It was realized that not including the Business Services administrator as a key stakeholder was a deterrent in the revision of the attendance coding system. Therefore, a pilot project proposal (refer to Appendix F) and presentation (refer to Appendix E) were presented to two district administrators. Analysis of the first semester attendance and academic outcomes of the 117 students, and recommendations to improve attendance tracking were disseminated during the presentation. The presentation also highlighted areas for improvement, such as inconsistencies in attendance tracking practices and lack of school nurse referral when there is illness chronic absence. At the conclusion of the presentation, the Chronic Illness Absence Verification form (Appendix B) was approved for district wide use. The

proposed Chronic Absence Policy, which includes a School Nurse referral process, is currently under review by district administrators. The projected date of implementation of the pilot project is August 2018.

Limitations

The data collected for this project was limited to ninth and tenth-grade students in a single large high school in a suburban Southern California community. Thus, findings might not be applicable to other grade levels. Another limitation is that almost half of the student population was Hispanic or Latino, and about 37% were eligible for free or reduced lunch. Findings might not be applicable to other ethnic or socioeconomic student groups.

CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

Conclusion

Among the 117 moderately to severely chronic absent students, 66% reported illness as the reason for the absences. Current attendance coding does not specifically identify illness related absences and documentation by attendance clerks varied widely. Because of the difficulty in identifying illness related absences, there was a lack of referral to the school nurse which might have mediated chronic absences due to illness.

Recommendations

Refine the Current Attendance Code

Make Code 1 specific to health-related absences (Table 31). This code would improve the process of tracking and more easily allow nurse referral for intervention for illness chronic absences.

Table 31.

Proposed Revised Attendance Codes

Excused Absence Code 1	Excused Absence Code 2
Illness or injury <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicate in narrative if the absence is per parent report or verified by a healthcare provider 	Court <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Court appearance Investigative hearing Jury duty Legal appointment Probation
Medical, dental, optometric, psychological, or chiropractic appointment	Employment conference
Hospitalization	Funeral service of <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Immediate family member (Mother, father, sibling, grandparent, spouse, in-law, or any other relative living in the home. Other (approved by administrator) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> California 1 day Out of State 3 days

Attendance Review and School Nurse Referral for Illness Absence

When a student has met the 10% absence threshold, attendance clerks determine if absences are coded as illness. If absence is related to illness, referring students to the school nurse is an essential step in ensuring that illness related chronic absences do not impede academic success. The school nurse would review the student's health and attendance history (for the current and previous school years) and contact the parent to verify the reason for the illness absences. If a medical condition is verified, school nurse care coordination would be initiated, which may include the development of an individualized health plan. The school nurse intervention could potentially promote improved school attendance. If there is lack of improvement in attendance after implementing the school nurse intervention, a SART meeting will be requested by the school nurse. If the school nurse determines that there is no confirmed medical condition, the case will be referred to the student's assigned administrator.

Implementation of Pilot Illness Absence Intervention Project

The pilot project will be implemented in August 2018. Site administrators, attendance clerks, and health clerks will receive training on the proposed attendance tracking and monitoring process outlined in the Chronic Absence Policy (Appendix C) and Chronic Absence Referral Algorithm (Appendix D). The school nurse will collect and analyze data described in the Evaluation phase.

Evaluation of the Pilot Program

At the conclusion of the pilot year, the following questions will be reviewed:

- Did a specific illness code facilitate quick identification of students with illness chronic absence?

- Did the attendance training result in consistent documentation and verification of absences?
- Were students with illness-related chronic absences identified prior to risk of academic failure?
- Did attendance clerks refer students with illness chronic absences to the school nurse for assessment and intervention?
- Did the Chronic Illness Verification form appropriately identify which absences were legitimately due to a medical condition?
- Did the nursing intervention(s) result in improved attendance?
- Was there a 10% reduction in SARB referrals as a result of early identification and intervention?

Implications for School Nursing Practice

This project is in line with a growing national movement to address underlying causes of chronic absenteeism, a risk factor for high school drop out, and find solutions to mitigate them. Chronic absenteeism is a warning sign for high-risk behaviors, results in lower educational success, and correlates with worse lifetime health (Eaton, Brener, & Kann, 2008; Henderson, Hill, & Norton, 2014; Vaughn, Maynard, Salas-Wright, Perron, & Abdon, 2013). The American Academy of Pediatrics released a policy statement highlighting the critical role school nurses have in promoting academic achievement, improved attendance, and better graduation rates (American Academy of Pediatrics Council on School Health, 2016). School nurses are in a position to identify unmet student health needs and key health risk factors that pose barriers in school attendance and success.

In 2013, the California Attorney General's Office released an annual California report which identified the scope, causes, and consequences of truancy and chronic absenteeism. The report and subsequent annual reports raised awareness about the attendance crisis in California schools (California Attorney General, 2016). The Every Student Succeeds Act of 2015 (ESSA), which replaced No Child Left Behind, requires states to report chronic absenteeism rates as a measure of student success. ESSA cites the leading role school nurses have in chronic disease management and in promoting student well being (Every Student Succeeds Act, 2015). Tracking illness related chronic absence and school nurse involvement would prompt nursing assessment and intervention, which may decrease absenteeism rates.

The *Step Up and Be Counted!* Initiative is a joint partnership between the National Association of School Nurses (NASN) and the National Association of State School Nurse Consultants. The aim of the initiative is to gather a uniformed data set across the country and identify the most effective nursing interventions. When working with chronically absent students, data collection is vital in determining what/if nursing intervention(s) were effective in improving health and educational outcomes. Data collection and analysis may aid in substantiating the role of school nurses in promoting health and education and help identify gaps and successes. Most school nurses are assigned multiple sites which pose a challenge in prioritizing their workload. Therefore, it is important to formulate school nurse interventions based on conclusions from data analysis and evidence-based practices.

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APPENDIX A

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 1

Chronic Health Conditions

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
Examine the effects of both physical and social functioning in reducing absenteeism in children with chronic illness (CI) Emerson, Distelberg, Morrell, Williams-Reade, Tapanes, & Montgomery, (2016).	Longitudinal design. IV: *MEND (family-based psychosocial intervention) DV: Absenteeism	Purposive sampling from LLUBMC. N=48 Caucasian children & adolescents (34 females, 14 males) & their parents (91.7% mothers). Inclusion criteria: -Age 8-18 -referred due to CI not optimally managed or had recently worsened -Enrolled in *MEND between Dec.2011-May 2014.	Demographics (age, gender, ethnicity, and type of illness) Missed school days Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory (PedsQL) - measures health-related quality of life (HRQOL) in 4 domains (physical, social, emotional & school). Individually rated by child and parent. - measured pre & post intervention	↑ parent-rated physical functioning associated with ↓ absences ↓ parent-rated social functioning associated with ↑ absences ↑ child-rated QOL associated with ↑ absences	Conclusions: Parent perceived physical and social functioning may have direct effect on school attendance. Limitations -Sample size reduced power of analyses -Potential incongruence between parent and child reports *MEND: 21-session/7 week intensive outpatient family therapy –base treatment protocol designed to improve adherence to medical regimens.
Examine the association between types of chronic health conditions (CHC)	Secondary analysis of *National Longitudinal Survey of	Cohort annually resurveyed from 1997-2009. N= 8984 youth	CHC= (1) asthma;(2) cancer, diabetes, epilepsy; (3)	N=22% reported CHC Odds of no HSC significantly higher in youth with CHC	Conclusion: Result of study demonstrated association between CHC and poor educational attainment. Also identified academic and

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
and educational attainment.	Youth (NLSY '97)-Cohort 1997.	Inclusion criteria: -Youth age 12-16 as of December 31, 1997.	heart condition; (4) other. Educational attainment-High school completion by age 21 (diploma or GED)	(asthma, cancer diabetes, epilepsy) ↑ absences with CHC; asthma highest rate of absenteeism Asthma & low educational attainment not associated with absences	psychosocial factors for youth with CHC. Findings may aid in development of preventive strategies to improve educational outcome. Limitations: -Secondary analysis. -Self-reported diagnosis. Parents who are more involved and knowledgeable of CHC may be more aware of participant's health. -Onset of CHC and limitations associated with not well understood. *NLSY '97: Nationally representative cohort of 8984 youths aged 12-16. Funded by Bureau of Labor Statistics. Used to collect data , such as youth labor force experiences, investment in education, training, government program participation, etc.
Champaloux & Young. (2015).	IV: CHC DV: Educational attainment	Authors: Champaloux- Univ. of Maryland School of Public Health Young- Researcher from Kaiser, Pasadena, CA	Absences= missed days of school per year		
Examine the association between chronic health conditions, school performance, & absenteeism.	Retrospective cohort study IV: Chronic health conditions (asthma, seizure disorder, ADHD, autism, mental health disorders, cardiovascular	Convenience sample N=22, 730 students enrolled in San Jose Unified School District, San Jose, CA, Inclusion criteria:	-CHC -Absent=full day of missed school -School performance: CST scores (ELA & math) -Gender -Grade level (2-11) -Ethnicity	-All CHC, except autism, associated with ↑ absenteeism (1.3x higher risk than those without CHC). -Students with mental health disorders had highest absentee rate resulting in ↓ math scores. -ADHD strongest association w/ ↓ ELA or math scores -Seizure disorder strong association w/	Conclusion: -Low school achievement is more strongly associated with ADHD, autism & seizure disorders than cardiovascular disorders or DM regardless of ethnicity, socioeconomic status or grade level. Unexplained correlation with absenteeism rate. -CHC, except autism, associated w/↑ absenteeism
Crump, Rivera, London, Landau, Erlendson, & Rodriguez (2013).					

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
	disorders, & DM). DV: 1) full-day school absences 2) CST scores (ELA & math)	-Student enrolled during 2007-2008, 2008-2009, & 2009-2010 school year -Grade 2 nd -11 th	-Primary language -Special Education -Parental income below 185% of federal poverty line -Parental education	↓ ELA -Asthma weakly associated with ↓ ELA or math scores	-↑ absenteeism=↓ ELA &/or math scores in students with asthma or mental health disorders. Limitations: 1. Parental report of CHC instead of a clinical diagnosis. Reliability of parental report is uncertain. 2. Information on intelligence & specific learning disability was unavailable. May affect CST performance.
Predict the probability of asthma in previously undiagnosed children by investigating the pattern of school absenteeism in asthmatic children within LA inner city school. Bonilla, S., Kehl, S., Kwong, K., Morphew, T., Kachru, R., et al. (2005).	Quantitative study Breathmobile asthma survey Survey question #3: Parents asked to recall how many school days child missed r/t respiratory symptoms during past year IV: asthma severity level DV: school absenteeism	Convenience sampling Public elementary school in urban LA N=528 Latino 92% Asian 2.7% Black 2.39% White 0.7%	0 absent days <5 absent days >10 absent days 3 groups: a. Known asthma b. High Probability Asthma (HPA) c. Low Probability Asthma (LPA)	Returned Survey results a. Population predominantly Hispanic b. 6.9% respondents w/confirmed asthma dx c. 9.2% HPA ↑absenteeism in younger students with known asthma & respiratory-related illness (average >2 school days) Underestimation of # absences by parents of children w/LPA Overestimation with known asthma	↑absenteeism in younger students with known asthma • 5 yr old children w/asthma missed school 2x more than HPA & LPA children & missed 2x more than 10-11 yr old children w/asthma • No difference in absenteeism rates at age 10-11 between known asthma, HPA & LPA • Asthma exacerbation more severe in younger children; may be correlates w/↑absenteeism Parent recall of absenteeism rate less accurate than school attendance records. In LA, school absenteeism maybe unreliable predictor of asthma in children; may not

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
					provide accurate view of burden of disease. ↑absenteeism likely represents greater asthma severity and/or inadequate asthma control Limitations: population predominantly Hispanic, and low socioeconomic level.

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
Investigate correlation between attitudes of HS students with/without asthma toward school health services, days absent, & academic achievement. Krenitsky-Korn, S. (2011).	-Non-experimental mixed methods design that combined survey approach with attendance & academic record Survey on Health Services in my School (to assess student perceptions of health services) IV: Attitudes toward school health services & absenteeism DV: 1) Days absent 2) Final grades in math and English	Convenience sample in a suburban HS of students (N=57). N=28 asthma N=29 without asthma Selectively chosen and matched by gender and existence of asthma Study conducted in 2004-2005 school year	Days absent: missed >3 periods measured in days Final grades: numeric grades Level of illness (asthma) 1) mild intermittent 2) mild persistent 3) moderate persistent 4) severe persistent	Attitudes 1) toward school health services: comfortable with receiving treatment in health office 2) absenteeism: felt they didn't feel they stayed home from school more than others in their grade Student with asthma ↑absenteeism (2x more) ↑willingness to be absent=↑absenteeism Students with asthma ↑absenteeism, ↓ scores in math & English No correlation between days absent with low level of asthma control or high level of illness Interventions or encouragement to stay in school after asthma tx reduced amount of missed schoolwork	Asthma related absence may pose student at risk for math failure due to sequential curricula School nurse intervention ↓early parent pick up, ↓loss of instruction Permissive attitudes toward absences highly r/t ↑absenteeism Recommendation: To better monitor absences, implement school policy that requires more precise reasons for absence Limitation: 1) Conducted at 1 suburban HS in New York City area 2) Sampling method 3) Sample size 4) Lack of control of confounders Implications to Nursing 1) SN case management can result in ↓absenteeism 2) Team approach to supporting students with asthma
Determine the difference in mean absence days between students	Cross-sectional comparison of asthma status and absenteeism	Predominantly AA schools district located in	<i>Asthma Symptomology</i> form: assesses frequency of	Prevalence: Varied significantly by grade level, race & gender 11.3% in elementary to 7% in HS	Asthma prevalence (9.7%) in this study higher than nation (8.7%); maybe due to population (↑ prevalence in

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
w/wo asthma, relationship between asthma severity and school absence, & if incident absences were due to asthma	IV: Asthma status and severity DV: Number of missed school days	St. Louis, Missouri N=9014 Subset of asthmatic students (9.7%; N=874) assessed for symptom severity & prospectively tracked to determine reason for absenteeism Predominantly AA & SES Data obtained during 2002-2003 school year	asthma symptoms Asthma severity: -mild intermittent mild persistent -moderate persistent -severe persistent Days absent Race (AA; White) Gender Grade (elementary, middle high)	2x greater in AA Males more likely to have asthma Asthma-missed +1.3 days/school yr -elementary w/asthma missed +1 days -middle school w/asthma +3 days Females w/asthma-missed +1.5 days/school yr compared to those w/o asthma AA w/asthma missed more days than AA w/o asthma (mean=9.1/8.0) ↑asthma severity=↑□□□□□□□□□□t Peaks of absence in Nov, Feb, March□	AA), low SES)- high risk for adverse asthma outcomes Study did not report on academic progress Students in this setting already at high risk for poor attendance Students w/greater than mild intermittent asthma severity missed +4.3 days 30% of illness related absences in students w/asthma r/t asthma specific symptoms Limitations: Asthma classified limited to information available to school nurse; may have resulted in underreporting Potential bias for tracking absenteeism. Reason for absence not challenged by school officials. No quantitative severity measure. Just self-report.
Moonie, S., Sterling, D., Figgs, L., & Castro, M. (2006)					

Table 2

Attendance Tracking

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
Utilized data to develop at-risk for high school (HS) drop out indicator for freshman class. Genao, S. (2015).	Convenience sample IV: Math & language scores in grades 6-8 DV: At-risk indicator	New Jersey school district 2673 HS freshman students (2008-2009)	Percent absent in grades 6-8 Math & language scores in grades 6-7	735 student considered at risk of HS transition based on math indicator 580 at risk based on language arts indicator 932 at risk based on attendance indicator	Conclusion: Reliable and readily available student data is needed to identify at risk students. Limitations: Author did not identify limitations.
Evaluate a school monitoring system that tracked cases of illness absences, specifically ILI [influenza-like illness (Fever >100°, feverish, cough, or sore throat)]. Short, V., Short, Marriott, C., Ostroff, S., & Waller, K. (2011).	Descriptive study On-line survey IV: Attendance tracking system DV: Survey results measuring acceptability, timeliness, & simplicity of attendance tracking system	Convenience sampling, Sept. 2009-June 2010. 367 Pennsylvania public school	Response rates of schools who participated and completed survey weekly used to determine the attendance tracking system for: 1) acceptability 2) timeliness 3) simplicity	1. Acceptance: 80% interested in continuing system 2. Timeliness: Data collected not current. 4-8 days out. 3. Simplicity of system: simple only if submitting data to 1 school. Otherwise time consuming	Conclusion: School-based sentinel system is a simple and reliable device for tracking absenteeism and ILI in schools. Limitations: 1) School absence records not reliable indicator of illness absences 2) Collecting illness data on all students unrealistic due to high daily absentee counts 3) Implementation occurred when there was high interest in H1N1 (swine flu), resulting in higher rate of participation 4) Not generalizable due to sample size and setting 5) Data was limited to 1 season of influenza

Table 3

School Nurse

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
Investigate the impact of school nurses (SN) in lowering absenteeism & associated cost related to care of poorly managed asthma. Rodriguez, E., Rivera, D., Perlroth, D., Becker, E., Wang, N., & Landau, M. (2014).	Quasi-experimental SNs received same asthma training IV: Asthma management w/FT SNs DV: Full day absences; cost savings (ADA funding)	2006-2009 school years 10 schools in San Jose, CA [4 schools with full-time (FT) SNs compared to 5 matched schools with part-time (PT) SNs; 1 school had school-based clinic] Pre-k-8 th graders N=6664	-# of full day absences/yr due to illness -ADA revenue limit -Demographics -Chronic health conditions; asthma	-↑ absenteeism with asthma -↓ mean illness absenteeism with FT SN -Potential savings of \$48,519 in ADA funding -Parents reported fewer asthma related visits	Improved asthma management with FT SN resulting in improved attendance, ADA savings, and reduced ER visits Limitations: 1. Limited generalizability. Schools selected had lower socioeconomic status. May have less access to care.
Identify the correlation between school nurse (SN) interventions & attendance. Weismuller, P., Grasska, M., Alexander, M., White, C., & Kramer, P. (2007).	Retrospective study IV: SN interventions DV: Absenteeism rate	Conducted in 2005 Randomly selected student folders (N=240) from 3 elementary schools in California suburb	-K-5 th graders -Demographics -Reason for SN referral -SN intervention used & outcome	-77.5% White students -Mean days of absences=4.7 -No SN referrals for absenteeism -SN interventions were predominantly r/t screening	1. No significant difference in absence rate pre- & post-SN intervention because no SN referrals were due to absenteeism concern 2. Few records documented nursing interventions or outcomes Limitations: 1. Predominantly white population in a California suburb 2. Lack of standardized documentation of health records-not ideal for data collection

Table 4

Truancy

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
Determine the effectiveness of a program that utilizes a school-based, court-engaged community truancy board with case management conducted by a school-based probation counselor in improving outcomes for youth with a history of truancy.	Quasi-experimental IV: School-based, court-engaged community truancy board with case management by PC utilizing the *Check & Connect (CC) model. DV: High school graduation at the conclusion of 2011-2012.	Paired sampling Inclusion criteria: -9 th graders between 2007-2009 with ≥ 5 unexcused absences in 1 month. -Student completed the 2008-2009 school year. -N=132 66 students from WVHS in Spokane, WA. 66 *matched sample from 1 out of 3 local area high schools	-Grade level (9, 10, 11) -Gender -Race/ethnicity (AIAN, Asian, Black, Hispanic, white) -Attendance: total absences & unexcused absences -Discipline: detention, in-school suspensions out-of-school suspensions, expulsions, total disciplinary events -Credits: attempted/earned -Incomplete -Transferred -GED -Graduated -Dropout	WVCTB group -Incomplete n=2 -Transferred n=7 -GED n=1 -Graduated n=46 -Dropout n=10 Matched control -Incomplete n=2 -Transferred n=13 -GED n=1 -Graduated n=32 -Dropout n=28	Conclusion: Graduation & GED completion rates were higher for intervention group (40% greater) & intervention group was 28% more likely to graduate than drop out. Limitations: 1. Study didn't allow for investigating effectiveness of intervention across risk level groups. 2. No random assignment. Possible that outcome may have resulted from pre-existing group differences. Notes: *Check and Connect Model: a comprehensive intervention designed to enhance school engagement and learning for marginalized, disengaged students in grades K-12 through relationship building, problem solving, persistence and capacity building.
Examine associations of HRB in HSS with being absent from school WP and WOP.	Secondary analysis from CDC study Cross sectional	Convenience sample of 9 th and 11 th grade students in 8 states (Did not identify which states).	Student information obtained from structured interviews	Female students: \uparrow absent WP Black and Hispanic students: \uparrow absent WOP	Conclusion 1. Absenteeism warning sign for HRB. 2. \uparrow absenteeism \rightarrow HRB 3. Implementation of Coordinated School Health Program (provides framework) improves attendance. 4. WOP HHS 2x risk for HRB.
Eaton, D., Brener, N., & Kann, L. (2008).	IV: HRB (categories: unintentional	Authors worked at CDC in Division of	Questionnaire identical to 2003 Youth Risk		

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
	injuries and violence, tobacco use, alcohol and other drug use, sexual behaviors) DV: absenteeism (WP/WOP)	Adolescent and School Health. N= 4178 students	Behavior Survey (YRBS). YRBS monitors 6 categories of priority health HRB among youth & young adults. Not absent (0 days) Absent WP or WOP (absent ≥1 day)	↑ prevalence absent WOP with student age Absent WP: increased risk HRB (25 of 55 behaviors) Absent WOP: increased risk HRB (43 of 55 behaviors); 2x greater risk than absent WP	Limitations 1. Chronically absent underrepresented due to likelihood of absence on data collection day. 2. Cross sectional. Unable to determine causality or pattern. 3. Data based on convenience sample. Demographic characteristic unrepresentative of national distribution. 4. Reason for absence unknown. 5. Did not check student's understanding of survey questions. May have interpreted it inaccurately affecting data results.
Purpose #1: Identify prevalence of truancy. Purpose #2: Determine SD and MH correlates of truancy. Purpose #3: Identify association between SE & SS Purpose #4: Identify association between PI & SS Purpose #5: Does extent of ESB ↑ likelihood of SS?	Secondary analysis from 2009 *NSDUH data Cross-sectional IV: ESB, PI, SE DV: SS (MDK or HSK)	Convenience sampling Inclusion criteria: ≥12 yo, residents of households, shelters, rooming houses, group homes, Alaska, Hawaii, civilians in military bases Interviewed in place of residence N= 18, 819 participants (age 12-17)	Computer-assisted interviewing: 1. personal interview 2. audio self-interviewing NSK=0 days MSK=1-3 days HSK=4 days FI 0=no; FI 1=yes WIP 0=no WIP 1=yes Age, Sex, AFI Race/ethnicity FH 0=no; FH 1=yes JDN; JDY LDN; LDY LAN; LAY	MSK: 9% HSK: 2% SD & MH correlates: • Older students ↑MSK, HSK • MSK=FH 0 • SS HHS 3x depressed & 2.5x anxiety than NSK HHS • MSK HHS ↑anxiety • HSK <\$75,000 AFI MSK, HSK= ↓	Conclusion 1. Truancy- significant problem in US. 2. Truancy correlated with substance abuse and ↑ESB, not SE (Problem Behavior Theory). 3. Truancy associated with ↓ parental involvement, ↓ grades. Limitations 1. Cross-sectional data. 2. Data based on self-report (may over or underreport problematic behaviors). 3. Did not address contextual or situational risks (i.e., neighborhood disadvantage). NSDUH= National Survey on Drug Use and health

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion, Study Limitations/Appropriateness
Perron, and Abdon (2013).			AH, ETOH, F, IDU, THC, YCH, YSID	SE, ↓ grades SS= ↓PI HSK=↑serious ESB	conducted by Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration Center for Behavioral Health Statistics and Quality Rockville, Maryland.

Notes: ADHD=attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. AFI=annual family income. AA=African American AH=attacked with intent to seriously harm. AIAN=American Indian & Alaska Native. CC=Check & Connect model. CHC=chronic health conditions. CHC=chronic health conditions (asthma, seizure disorder, ADHD, autism, mental health disorders, cardiovascular disorders, & DM). Defined chronic if reported in each of the first 2 study years. CI=chronic illness. CST=California Standards Test. DM=diabetes mellitus. DV=dependent variable. ELA=English language arts. ESB= externalizing spectrum of behaviors (AH, ETOH, F, IDU, THC, YCH, YSID). ETOH= alcohol use. F=fight at school/work. FH= father in the home. FI=father incarcerated in the past year. GED: Graduate equivalency degree. HRB= health risk behaviors. HS=High school. HSC=high school completion either with diploma or GED. HSS=high school students. IV= independent variable. JDN=jail/detention no. JDY=jail/detention yes. LAN=lifetime anxiety no. LAY=lifetime anxiety yes. LDN=lifetime depression no. LDY=lifetime depression yes. LLUBMC=Loma Linda University Behavioral Medical Center. MEND=Mastering Each New Direction. MH= mental health. MSK=moderate skipping school. NSK=non-school skipping. PC=probation counselor/truancy specialist. PI=parental involvement. SD= socio-demographic. SE= school engagement. SES= socioeconomic status. SS=skipping school. THC=marijuana use. w/o=without. WIP=worked in past year. WOP=without permission. WP=with permission. WVCTB: intervention consisted of mentoring, systematic academic mentoring, timely individualized intervention, and enhanced home engagement). WVHS=West Valley High School. YCH=youth carried handgun. yo=years old. YSID=youth sold illegal drugs.

APPENDIX B

CHRONIC ILLNESS ABSENCE VERIFICATION

Date _____

Student _____ DOB _____ ID# _____ Grade _____

Dear Medical Provider,

Your patient is a student enrolled in the Corona-Norco Unified School District. For our records, please list the **chronic illness diagnosed** for the student. Also, please check or list symptoms that would not warrant an office visit, but might require the child to stay home from school. This will allow the parent to verify illnesses, by listing in writing to the school the symptoms designated below, without bringing the child to your office for an examination. This document **expires** at the end of the academic year it was received.

Chronic Illness/Medical Diagnosis _____

Symptoms _____

Expected **frequency** of episodes of symptoms _____ AND **length** of absence per episode _____ days (for example: monthly, 4 times per school year, etc.)**Neurological System**

blurred vision
 ___ dizziness/unsteadiness
 ___ grand mal seizures
 ___ lethargy
 ___ numbness in extremities
 ___ petit mal seizures
 ___ severe headache

Integumentary

___ edema
 ___ infections
 ___ skin lesions

Musculoskeletal system

___ inflammation swelling
 ___ pain

Respiratory System

congested airway
 ___ difficulty breathing
 ___ pain
 ___ pallor/cyanosis
 ___ persistent coughing
 ___ weakness/fatigue

Cardiovascular system

___ arrhythmia
 ___ fevers/infections
 ___ pain
 ___ pallor/cyanosis
 ___ palpitations
 ___ rapid pulse
 ___ weakness/dizziness

Gastrointestinal System

abdominal pain
 ___ constipation
 ___ diarrhea
 ___ nausea/vomiting

Genitourinary system

___ bladder/kidney infection
 fever

Ear, Nose, & Throat

___ chronic infections
 ___ fever
 ___ pneumonia/bronchitis
 ___ severe allergies
 severe asthma

Additional comments _____

Physician's Signature _____ Physician's Printed Name _____ Office Phone Number _____	Office Seal/Stamp
--	-------------------

Release of Medical Information

As the parent or guardian of the above-named pupil, I hereby give permission for the Release of Medical Information from the physician who may be contacted by the School Nurse as needed for clarification.

Permiso para el intercambio de informacion medica

Como padre a tutor del alumno arriba mencionado, por medio de la presentada o mi permiso para que el medico tratante Intercambie informacion medica con enfermera de escuela este necesite clarificacion.

Parent/Guardian Signature/Firma del Padre _____ Date/Fecha _____

ATTENDANCE CLERK: Provide a copy of the completed form to the School Nurse.

Adapted from California Department Education Chronic Illness Sample Verification Form (3/28/18).

APPENDIX C

CHRONIC ABSENCE POLICY

When missed school days have reached the 10% absence threshold (irrespective of excused or unexcused absences), an attendance clerk will review reasons for absences. Chronic absence related to illness will trigger a referral to a school nurse. If the absence is not illness related, the attendance clerk will make a referral to an administrator.

Absences Due to Student Illness

A. Method of Verification

Absences due to illness, including a doctor's appointment during the school day, may be considered verified in the following ways:

1. Physician's verification via note, email, or fax.
2. School Nurse/Principal's exchange with parent/guardian via a phone conversation, on site visit, email or written note.
3. Visit to the student's home by the Principal/School Nurse or any other investigative method that confirms that the student was absent for the reasons stated.

Students are encouraged to always bring a physician's note when possible if an appointment interferes with any part of a school day.

B. School Nurse Referral Process

1. If reasons for the absence is reported as medically related and the 10% missed school days threshold has been reached, the attendance clerk will make a referral to the school nurse.
2. The school nurse will review the student's health and attendance history (for the current and previous school years).
3. The school nurse will contact parent to verify reason for absences.
 - a. If there is no confirmed medical condition, the case will be referred to the student's assigned administrator.
 - b. If a medical condition is verified, school nurse care coordination will be initiated, which may include the development of a health action plan.
4. If attendance does not improve after school nurse care coordination efforts, the school nurse will initiate a School Attendance Review Team (SART) meeting request.

Non-Illness Related Absences

When a student is identified as a chronic absentee (absences have reached the 10% absence threshold) and the reason is not illness related, the attendance clerk will refer the case to the administrator assigned to the student.

A. Contact By Administrator

1. The administrator shall communicate with the student's parent/guardian to determine reason(s) for the excessive absences, ensure the student and parent/guardian are aware of the adverse consequences of poor attendance, and jointly develop a plan for improving the student's school attendance.

2. If attendance does not improve after the administrator's efforts, a SART referral will be initiated.

If attendance does not improve after the SART process, a Student Attendance Review Board (SARB) referral will be initiated.

APPENDIX D

CHRONIC ABSENCE REFERRAL ALGORITHM

APPENDIX E

PILOT PROJECT PROPOSAL PRESENTATION

Chronic absenteeism is also linked with serious health issues into adulthood.

Adults with fewer education

- More likely to **die prematurely**
- Engage in **unhealthy behaviors**
- Higher rates of **diabetes** and **obesity**
- **Higher infant mortality rates** among children born to women without a high school education

Robert Wood Johnson Foundation Health Policy Brief (2016)

Objectives

- Review analysis of ERHS attendance data
- Review attendance tracking practices
- Proposal to improve current practices

ERHS DATA

ERHS Attendance Data

District Attendance by Grade by Year - High (Grade 9-12)

Selected School: 755 Today: 3/29/2018

GRADE	NUMBER severe chronic absence	PERCENT severe chronic absence	NUMBER moderate chronic absence	PERCENT moderate chronic absence	NUMBER ALL chronic absence (severe + moderate)	PERCENT ALL chronic absence (severe + moderate)	NUMBER at-risk attendance	PERCENT at-risk attendance	NUMBER satisfactory attendance	PERCENT satisfactory attendance	Total Students
2017 - 2018											
Grade 9	21	1.7%	60	4.8%	81	6.4%	171	13.6%	1,008	80.0%	1,260
Grade 10	22	1.9%	47	4.1%	69	6.0%	185	16.2%	887	77.7%	1,141
Grade 11	19	1.7%	63	5.5%	82	7.2%	204	17.9%	853	74.9%	1,139
Grade 12	24	2.3%	84	8.2%	108	10.5%	223	21.7%	696	67.8%	1,027
Totals	86	1.9%	254	5.6%	340	7.4%	783	17.1%	3,444	75.4%	4,567
2016 - 2017											
Grade 9	9	0.8%	45	3.9%	54	4.7%	162	14.0%	939	81.3%	1,155
Grade 10	25	2.1%	63	5.4%	88	7.6%	188	16.1%	889	76.3%	1,165
Grade 11	23	2.1%	64	5.9%	87	8.0%	191	17.6%	808	74.4%	1,086
Grade 12	17	1.7%	106	10.3%	123	12.6%	254	26.1%	598	61.3%	975
Totals	74	1.7%	278	6.3%	352	8.0%	795	18.1%	3,234	73.8%	4,381
2015 - 2016											
Grade 9	15	1.2%	58	4.8%	73	6.0%	159	13.2%	970	80.7%	1,202
Grade 10	19	1.7%	70	6.2%	89	7.9%	184	16.3%	854	75.8%	1,127
Grade 11	20	1.9%	72	7.0%	92	8.9%	176	17.1%	764	74.0%	1,032
Grade 12	15	1.7%	96	9.5%	111	11.2%	214	23.7%	587	65.1%	902
Totals	69	1.6%	286	6.7%	355	8.3%	733	17.2%	3,175	74.5%	4,263

Definitions

- **Illness absence:** Missed a full school day due to a reported illness or a health related appointment (i.e. doctor's visit, mental health, or dental).
- **Illness chronic absence criteria:** $\geq 51\%$ of absences was deemed an illness absence
- **Clustered absence:** Missed ≥ 4 consecutive school days due to health

ERHS Data

By Absence Category						
Grade	Moderate CA N	Moderate ICA N (%)	Severe CA N	Severe ICA N (%)	Total Moderate & Severe CA N	Total Moderate & Severe ICA N (%)
9	42	30(71)	13	6(46)	55	36(65)
10	49	36(73)	13	5(38)	62	41(66)
Total	91	66(73)	26	11(42)	117	77 (66)

Note: CA=Chronic Absence. ICA=Illness Chronic Absence. 66% reported illness as the primary reason for the absences.

ERHS Data

Students with Clustered Illness Chronic Absences						
Grade	Moderate ICA N	Moderate CICA N(%)	Severe ICA N	Severe CICA N (%)	Total Moderate & Severe ICA N	Total Moderate & Severe CICA N(%)
9	30	7 (23)	6	3 (50)	36	10 (28)
10	36	12 (33)	5	4 (80)	41	16 (39)
Total	66	19 (29)	11	7 (64)	77	26 (34)

Note: ICA=Illness Chronic Absence. CICA=Clustered Illness Chronic Absences. 34% of students had clustered absences.

ERHS Data

Academic Outcome of Illness Chronic Absences						
Grade	Moderate illness chronic absence N=66			Severe illness chronic absence N=11		
	N	Failed ≥ 1 Class N(%)	Excessive Absences Affected Progress N	N	Failed ≥ 1 class N(%)	Excessive Absences Affected Progress N
9	30	3(10)	5(17)	6	1(17)	1((17)
10	36	4(11)	7(19)	5	3(60)	4(80)
Total	66	7(11)	12(18)	11	4(36)	5(45)

Note: Of 77 students, 17% failed ≥ 1 classes.

Attendance Codes

Excused Absence Code 1	Excused Absence Code 2
Illness or injury	Religious holiday, ceremony or retreat
Medical, dental, optometric, psychological, or chiropractic appointment	Employment conference
Funeral service of immediate family member (Mother, father, sibling, grandparent, spouse, in-law, or any other relative living in the home. California- 1 day Out of State- 3days	Funeral service other than excused
Jury Duty	Court appearance/probation/legal appointment/investigative hearing
Teen parent to care for sick child	Personal reason requested by parent or guardian-approved by administrator or administrative designee

Period	January 2018	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
HR																			2					1								
1																			2	2				1	1							
2																			2	2				1	1	1						
3																			2	2				1	1	1						
4																			2	2				2	1	1						
5																			2	2				2	1	1						
6																			2	2				2	1	1					E	

Period	February 2018	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28		
HR																															
1																															
2																															
3																															
4																															
5																															
6																															

1																															
2																															
3																															
4																															
5																															
6																															

Attendance	Date	Per	Course	Teacher	Room	Cycle Day	Scheduled
Excused Absence	01/23/2018	1	917501-30 HEALTH	Singleton, Stephen	B214	Odd	01/16/2018 - 06/01/2018

Ill per mom/rcvdr note

PILOT PROJECT PROPOSAL

Goals of Pilot

- ↓ **SARB** referrals due to illness chronic absences
- **Early identification** of students at risk
- Appropriate education placement
- Improved attendance

Key Personnel to Track Illness Chronic Absences

Restructure Absence Codes

66%
reported
illness as
primary
reason for
absences

Excused Absence Code 1	Excused Absence Code 2
Illness or injury <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicate in narrative if the absence is per parent report or verified by a healthcare provider 	Court <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Court appearance Investigative hearing Jury duty Legal appointment Probation
Medical, dental, optometric, psychological, or chiropractic appointment	Employment conference
Hospitalization	Funeral service of <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Immediate family member (Mother, father, sibling, grandparent, spouse, in-law, or any other relative living in the home. Other (approved by administrator) California- 1 day Out of State- 3days

Implement a Revised Attendance Policy

- Generate monthly reports
- 10% absence threshold

Non-Illness Related Absences

When a student is identified as a chronic absentee (absences have reached the 10% absence threshold) and the reason is not illness related, the attendance clerk would refer the case to the administrator assigned to the student.

A. Administrator Contact

1. The administrator shall communicate with the student's parent/guardian to determine reason(s) for the excessive absences, ensure the student and parent/guardian are aware of the adverse consequences of poor attendance, and jointly develop a plan for improving the student's school attendance.
2. If attendance does not improve after the administrator's efforts, a SART referral will be initiated.

If attendance does not improve after the SART process, a Student Attendance Review Board (SARB) referral will be initiated.

Implementation of an Illness Absence Policy

- Consistent verification practices
- Integrate a school nurse referral process

Absences Due to Student Illness

A. Method of Verification

Absences due to illness, including a doctor's appointment during the school day, may be considered verified in the following ways:

1. Physician's verification via note, email, or fax.
2. School Nurse/Principal's exchange with parent/guardian via a phone conversation, on site visit, email or written note.
3. Visit to the student's home by the Principal/School Nurse or any other investigative method which confirms that the student was absent for the reasons stated.

Students are encouraged to bring a physician's note when possible if an appointment interferes with any part of a school day.

B. School Nurse Referral Process

1. If reasons for the absence is reported as medically related and the 10% missed school days threshold has been reached, the attendance clerk will make a referral to the school nurse.
2. The school nurse will review the student's health and attendance history (for the current and previous school years).
3. The school nurse will contact parent to verify reason for absences.
 - a. If there is no confirmed medical condition, the case will be referred to the student's assigned administrator.
 - b. If a medical condition is verified, school nurse care coordination will be initiated, which may include the development of a health action plan.
4. If attendance does not improve after school nurse care coordination efforts, the school nurse will discuss the situation with an administrator and consider the initiation of a School Attendance Review Team (SART) referral process.

Verify Chronic Illness Diagnosis

CHRONIC ILLNESS ABSENCE VERIFICATION

Date _____

Student _____ DOB _____ ID# _____ Grade _____

Dear Medical Provider,
Your patient is a student enrolled in the Corona-Norco Unified School District. For our records, please list the chronic illness diagnosed for the student. Also, please check or list symptoms that would not warrant an office visit, but might require the child to stay home from school. This will allow the parent to verify illnesses, by listing in writing to the school the symptoms designated below, without bringing the child to your office for an examination. This document expires at the end of the academic year it was received.

Chronic Illness Medical Diagnosis _____

Symptoms _____

Expected frequency of episodes of symptoms _____ AND length of absence per episode _____ days (for example: monthly, 4 times per school year, etc.)

Neurological System blurred vision dizziness/vertigo grand mal seizures jerburry numbness in extremities petit mal seizures severe headache	Respiratory System congested airway difficulty breathing pain pallor/cyanosis persistent coughing weakness/fatigue	Gastrointestinal System abdominal pain constipation diarrhea nausea/vomiting
Integumentary edema infections skin lesions	Cardiovascular system arrhythmia fevers/infections pain pallor/cyanosis palpitations rapid pulse weakness/dizziness	Genitourinary system bladder/kidney infection fever
Musculoskeletal system inflammation/swelling pain		Ear, Nose, & Throat chronic infections fever pneumonia/bronchitis severe allergies severe asthma

Additional comments _____

Physician Signature _____	Office Seal/Stamp _____
Physician's Printed Name _____	
Office Phone Number _____	

Release of Medical Information
As the parent or guardian of the above-named pupil, I hereby give permission for the Release of Medical Information from the physician who may be contacted by the School Nurse as needed for clarification.

Permiso para el intercambio de información médica
Como padre o tutor del alumno arriba mencionado, por medio de la presente doy mi permiso para que el médico entregue información médica con el personal de la escuela si es necesario para clarificación.

Parent/Guardian Signature/Firma del Padre _____ Date/Fecha _____

ATTENDANCE CLERK: Provide a copy of the completed form to the School Nurse.
Adapted from California Department of Education Chronic Illness Sample Verification Form (3-28-14).

- Refer chronic and clustered illness absences to the school nurse
- Refer truancies to site administrator

	Description of Work	Anticipated Costs (Salary plus benefits)
Phase One- Three	<p>ATTENDANCE CLERKS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generate the district attorney attendance list on a monthly basis to identify students who meet the moderate to severe chronic absence threshold. Review the reasons for absences. If ≥ 51% of absences is due to illness, complete a school nurse referral <p>SCHOOL NURSE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review health records of top 10 chronically ill students who were referred, contact with parents &/or health care provider 	<p>1 hour per attendance clerk= \$60 per month</p> <p>\$60 x 4=\$240 per month \$240 x 8 months=\$1920</p> <p>Total 10 hours x \$95=\$950/month \$950x8 months= \$7,600</p>
Phase Four	School nurse will analyze, evaluate, and disseminate pilot project results.	\$95x10 hours=\$950
Annual Cost	Total	\$10,470

Evaluation of Pilot Project

Criteria:

- Specific **illness absence code** established by 8/1/18
- Students with chronic absence due to health referred to **school nurse**

Evaluation of Pilot Project

- **Nursing intervention plan** ↓ chronic absence due to illness
- **10% reduction in SARB referrals** as a result of early intervention with illness chronic absences
- Proposed illness chronic absence policy & the verification form **appropriately identified** which illness chronic absences were legitimately due to a medical condition

Summary

Analysis: Moderate-Severe Absences in 9th & 10th Graders

- **66%** reported **illness** as the primary reason for the absences
- **34%** **clustered** illness absences
- **14%** with chronic absences due to illness **failed ≥ 1 class** in semester 1

Summary

Attendance Tracking Practices

- Difficult to decipher reason for absences
- Inconsistent absence monitoring/documentation practices
- School nurse not notified of illness absences

Summary: Pilot Project Proposal

Attendance Clerks

1. Generate the district attorney attendance list on a monthly basis
2. Refer cases to school nurse if $\geq 51\%$ of absences is due to illness

School Nurse

1. Review health records of top 10 chronically ill students
2. Analyze, evaluate, and disseminate pilot project results.

APPENDIX F

Proposal for

Pilot Project for Early Intervention to
Address Illness Chronic Absences

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I. Summary

- **Purpose.** To implement a pilot project at Roosevelt High School which focuses on early identification of students who are at risk for poor academic outcomes due to chronic absence. Key components of this pilot project include:
 1. Differentiation between truancies and illness absences. Illness was the primary reason for absences in 66% of ninth and tenth graders who reached at least the moderate chronic absence category.
 2. Establish consistency in attendance monitoring practices. Specify absences due to illness.
 3. Implementation of early intervention strategies to mitigate chronic absence. Refer illness chronic and clustered absences to the school nurse.
- **Anticipated Result of Pilot Project Proposal.**
 1. Decrease the number of SARB referrals due to illness chronic absences.
 2. Early identification of students at risk of course failure due to excessive absences.
 3. Appropriate education placement prior to grades being negatively affected due to illness chronic absences.
- **Type and Support Requested.**
 1. Attendance clerks;
 - Generate monthly attendance report, including the District Attorney's Report.
 - Identify students with illness chronic absences and refer to the school nurse
 2. Establish a specific illness code OR revise the current absence coding system.
- **Total Anticipated Budget.**
 1. Attendance Clerks 1 hour per attendance clerk= \$60 per month
\$60 x 4 clerks=\$240/month
 2. School Nurse: Total 10 hours x \$95=\$950/month

II. Needs/Problems

The three-year average rate of moderate to chronic absences in 9th grade students is **5.7%**. The rate for 10th graders is slightly higher at **7.2%**.

District Attendance by Grade by Year - High (Grade 9-12)												
Selected School: 750											Today: 3/29/2018	
GRADE	NUMBER severe chronic absence	PERCENT severe chronic absence	NUMBER moderate chronic absence	PERCENT moderate chronic absence	NUMBER All chronic absence (severe + moderate)	PERCENT All chronic absence (severe + moderate)	NUMBER at risk attendance	PERCENT at risk attendance	NUMBER satisfactory attendance	PERCENT satisfactory attendance	Total Students	
2017 - 2018												
Grade 9	31	1.7%	65	4.8%	96	6.5%	173	13.3%	1,027	86.7%	1,200	
Grade 10	32	1.8%	47	4.1%	79	5.9%	189	16.3%	917	77.7%	1,144	
Grade 11	36	1.7%	43	3.9%	79	3.2%	206	17.9%	973	84.9%	1,130	
Grade 12	24	2.3%	84	8.2%	108	10.3%	223	21.7%	899	87.9%	1,017	
Totals	86	5.9%	254	5.9%	340	7.4%	793	17.1%	5,446	75.8%	4,547	
2016 - 2017												
Grade 9	31	2.3%	41	3.8%	72	4.7%	162	14.3%	1,016	87.2%	1,111	
Grade 10	33	2.1%	42	3.4%	75	5.5%	189	16.1%	1,016	79.2%	1,162	
Grade 11	33	2.1%	44	3.9%	77	4.4%	193	17.8%	930	82.2%	1,088	
Grade 12	33	1.7%	108	10.9%	141	10.6%	244	28.1%	1,000	81.9%	1,111	
Totals	78	5.7%	238	6.2%	316	8.9%	790	18.1%	5,234	75.8%	4,383	
2015 - 2016												
Grade 9	31	1.2%	39	4.8%	70	6.7%	133	12.2%	936	88.7%	1,050	
Grade 10	33	1.7%	70	5.2%	103	7.9%	192	16.3%	1,044	79.9%	1,137	
Grade 11	35	1.9%	72	5.8%	107	6.7%	193	17.1%	1,024	84.9%	1,192	
Grade 12	35	1.7%	80	8.0%	115	11.2%	218	23.7%	867	80.1%	900	
Totals	86	5.8%	261	6.2%	346	8.3%	736	17.2%	5,171	74.9%	4,263	

An attendance report generated on March 2, 2018, identified 117 students who met the moderate or chronic absence criteria (missed at least 10% of school days). The attendance data, academic achievement, and health status of these students were reviewed and analyzed. **Illness** was the primary reason for absences in **66%** of ninth and tenth graders who reached at least the moderate chronic absence category. Thirty-four percent of ninth and tenth graders with illness chronic absences had clustered absences (missed four or more consecutive days of school).

Students by Absence Category						
Grade	Moderate CA	Moderate ICA	Severe CA	Severe ICA	Total Moderate and Severe CA	Total Moderate and Severe ICA
	N	N (%)	N	N (%)	N	N (%)
9	42	30 (71)	13	6 (46)	55	36 (65)
10	49	36 (73)	13	5 (38)	62	41 (66)
Total	91	66 (73)	26	11 (42)	117	77 (66)

Note: CA=Chronic Absence. ICA=Illness Chronic Absence. Of 117 students in the 9th and 10th grade with moderate to severe chronic absences, **66% reported illness** as the primary reason for the absences.

Of 30 ninth graders with moderate illness chronic absences, 10% failed one or more courses and teachers reported that excessive absences affected academic progress in 17% of these students. Teachers cited excessive absences as the reason one of the six students (17%) in the severe illness chronic absence category failed one or more courses. Of 36 tenth graders, 11% failed one or more classes, and teachers cited chronic absences affected academic progress. Students with severe illness absences had poorer academic outcomes.

Academic Outcome of Illness Chronic Absences						
Grade	Moderate Chronic Illness Absence N=66			Severe Chronic Illness Absence N=11		
	N	Failed ≥1 Class N (%)	Excessive Absences Affected Progress N (%)	N	Failed ≥1 Class N (%)	Excessive Absences Affected Progress N (%)
9	30	3 (10)	5 (17)	6	1 (17)	1 (17)
10	36	4 (11)	7 (19)	5	3 (60)	4 (80)
Total	66	7 (11)	12 (18)	11	4 (36)	5 (45)

Note: The failed course(s) occurred during the first semester of the current school year. Of 77 students with moderate to severe illness chronic absences, 14% failed one or more classes in the first semester.

Chronic absences due to a health-related concern (i.e. "sick", medical/ dental/ therapy appointments, injury, or hospitalization) are not routinely referred to the school nurse. The lack of an illness code and an established school referral process for illness chronic absences may impede early intervention strategies.

III. Goals/Objectives

1. Goal 1: Establish an illness code to easily identify students with illness chronic absence.
2. Goal 2: Top 10 students with illness chronic absences would be referred to the school nurse to validate reasons for absence. This process would allow the differentiation between truancies and valid illness absence.
3. Goal 3: Clustered illness absences (4 consecutive missed school days) would be referred to the school nurse to determine if school nurse interventions (i.e. develop a health plan) are needed.
4. Goal 4: Early identification of the top 10 students would facilitate early intervention, including ensuring academic success.
5. Goal 5: Establish consistency in attendance tracking practices (i.e. selecting the correct code for the absence, proper documentation of the reason for absence, and following the chronic absence monitoring algorithm).
- 6.

IV. Procedures

Refer to Appendix A, B, and C.

V. Timetable

	Description of Work	Start and End Dates
Phase One	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendance clerks to run an attendance report and identify students who met the moderate to severe illness absence threshold and has either cluster absences or history of illness chronic absences Attendance clerks to refer top 10 students to school nurse 	October 1-November 1
Phase Two	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendance clerks to identify students who met the moderate to severe absence threshold and are in danger of failing ≥ 1 class Differentiate between truancies & illness absences Attendance clerks to refer top 10 students to school nurse 	Quarter 1 Progress
Phase Three	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendance clerks to identify students who met the moderate to severe absence threshold and failed ≥ 1 class due to illness chronic absence 	End of 1 st semester
Phase Four	School nurse will analyze, evaluate, and disseminate pilot project results.	End of 2 nd semester

V. Budget

	Description of Work	Anticipated Costs (Salary plus benefits)
Phase One-Three	<p>ATTENDANCE CLERKS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generate the district attorney attendance list on a monthly basis to identify students who meet the moderate to severe chronic absence threshold. Review the reasons for absences. If $\geq 51\%$ of absences is due to illness, complete a school nurse referral <p>SCHOOL NURSE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review health records of top 10 chronically ill students who were referred, contact with parents &/or health care provider 	<p>1 hour per attendance clerk \$60 per month</p> <p>\$60 x 4=\$240 per month \$240 x 8 months=\$1920</p> <p>Total 10 hours x \$95=\$950/month \$950x8 months=\$7,600</p>
Phase Four	School nurse will analyze, evaluate, and disseminate pilot project results.	\$95x10 hours=\$950
Annual Cost	Total	\$10,470

Costs Associated with Higher Level Intervention Strategies

Intervention Plan	Activity to Address Consequence of illness chronic absence	Anticipated Costs
SART 1 hour	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Gather attendance history, progress grades, teacher input SART Meeting 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Administrator (\$180) Nurse (\$95) Teachers (\$95)
SARB 1 hour	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Gather attendance history, progress grades, teacher input, school site intervention strategies Attend SARB Meeting 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> School site administrator (\$150) SARB Panel (SARB coordinator, Family Center Director & staff, School Nurse, School Counselor, School Psychologist, CWA worker, CPS supervisor, Probation, Corona PD- \$800)
Credit Recovery for Failed Classes	Summer School	Unknown cost per student

VI. Key Personnel

VII. Evaluation

Effectiveness of the proposed pilot will be evaluated by the following criteria:

- A specific illness absence code will be established by August 1, 2018.
- The attendance history of the top 10 students with severe chronic absence will be reviewed at the end of the first quarter to determine if there was consistency amongst attendance clerks in documentation of the reasons for the absences
- The attendance clerks referred students with illness chronic absence to the school nurse.
- The school nurse conducted an assessment of the student's attendance and health history, and developed a nursing intervention plan to mitigate illness chronic absences.
- Early intervention with illness chronic absences will result in a 25% reduction in SARB referrals.
- The proposed illness chronic absence policy and the verification form will appropriately identify which illness chronic absences were legitimately due to a medical condition.

VIII. Next Steps

Success of the proposed pilot project is contingent on:

- The establishment of a specific illness code so that these absences can be easily identified and aggregated.
- Administrative support to implement an absence monitoring process that will allow attendance clerks, the health clerk, and school nurse to track students with illness chronic absences.

Appendix A

Chronic Absence Policy

When missed school days have reached the 10% absence threshold (irrespective of excused or unexcused absences), an attendance clerk will review reasons for absences. Chronic absence related to illness will trigger a referral to a school nurse. If the absence is not illness related, the attendance clerk will make a referral to an administrator.

Absences Due to Student Illness**A. Method of Verification**

Absences due to illness, including a doctor's appointment during the school day, may be considered verified in the following ways:

1. Physician's verification via note, email, or fax.
2. School Nurse/Principal's exchange with parent/guardian via a phone conversation, on site visit, email or written note.
3. Visit to the student's home by the Principal/School Nurse or any other investigative method which confirms that the student was absent for the reasons stated.

Students are encouraged to bring a physician's note when possible if an appointment interferes with any part of a school day.

B. School Nurse Referral Process

1. If reasons for the absence is reported as medically related and the 10% missed school days threshold has been reached, the attendance clerk will make a referral to the school nurse.
2. The school nurse will review the student's health and attendance history (for the current and previous school years).
3. The school nurse will contact parent to verify reason for absences.
 - a. If there is no confirmed medical condition, the case will be referred to the student's assigned administrator.
 - b. If a medical condition is verified, school nurse care coordination will be initiated, which may include the development of a health action plan.
4. If attendance does not improve after school nurse care coordination efforts, the school nurse will discuss the situation with an administrator and consider the initiation of a School Attendance Review Team (SART) referral process.

Non-Illness Related Absences

When a student is identified as a chronic absentee (absences have reached the 10% absence threshold) and the reason is not illness related, the attendance clerk would refer the case to the administrator assigned to the student.

A. Administrator Contact

1. The administrator shall communicate with the student's parent/guardian to determine reason(s) for the excessive absences, ensure the student and parent/guardian are aware of the adverse consequences of poor attendance, and jointly develop a plan for improving the student's school attendance.
2. If attendance does not improve after the administrator's efforts, a SART referral will be initiated.

If attendance does not improve after the SART process, a Student Attendance Review Board (SARB) referral will be initiated.

Appendix B

Chronic Absence Monitoring Algorithm

Appendix C

ILLNESS CHRONIC ABSENCE VERIFICATION

Date _____

Student _____ DOB _____ ID# _____ Grade _____

Dear Medical Provider,

Your patient is a student enrolled in the Corona-Norco Unified School District. For our records, please list the **chronic illness diagnosed** for the student. Also, please check or list symptoms that would not warrant an office visit, but might require the child to stay home from school. This will allow the parent to verify illnesses, by listing in writing to the school the symptoms designated below, without bringing the child to your office for an examination. This document **expires** at the end of the academic year it was received.

Chronic Illness/Medical Diagnosis _____

Symptoms _____

Expected frequency of episodes of symptoms _____ AND length of absence per episode _____ days (for example: monthly, 4 times per school year, etc.)

Neurological System

blurred vision
 dizziness/unsteadiness
 grand mal seizures
 lethargy
 numbness in extremities
 petit mal seizures
 severe headache

Integumentary

edema
 infections
 skin lesions

Musculoskeletal system

inflammation/swelling
 pain

Respiratory System

congested airway
 difficulty breathing
 pain
 pallor/cyanosis
 persistent coughing
 weakness/fatigue

Cardiovascular system

arrhythmia
 fevers/infections
 pain
 pallor/cyanosis
 palpitations
 rapid pulse
 weakness/dizziness

Gastrointestinal System

abdominal pain
 constipation
 diarrhea
 nausea/vomiting

Genitourinary system

bladder/kidney infection
 fever

Ear, Nose, & Throat

chronic infections
 fever
 pneumonia/bronchitis
 severe allergies
 severe asthma

Additional comments _____

Physician's Signature _____ Physician's Printed Name _____ Office Phone Number _____	Office Seal/Stamp
--	-------------------

Release of Medical Information

As the parent or guardian of the above-named pupil, I hereby give permission for the Release of Medical Information from the physician who may be contacted by the School Nurse as needed for clarification.

Permiso para el intercambio de informacion medica

Como padre o tutor del alumno arriba mencionado, por medio de la presentada oy mi permiso para que el medico tratante Intercambie informacion medica con enfermera de escuela este necesite clarificación.

Parent/Guardian Signature/Firma del Padre _____ Date/Fecha _____

ATTENDANCE CLERK: Provide a copy of the completed form to the School Nurse.

Adapted from California Department Education Chronic Illness Sample Verification Form (3/28/18).